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Workshop reports

**Successful and timely
uptake of artificial
intelligence in science
in the EU**

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Scientific process workshop report

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Introduction

Evidence-gathering expert workshops are a vital part of SAPEA's rapid evidence review process. Together with the literature reviews, they constitute the main avenue for evidence gathering from the wider scientific community.

This evidence-gathering workshop for the topic *Successful and timely uptake of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in science in the EU* addressed Key Area 2 of the scoping paper:¹ 'The impact of AI on the Scientific Process'. It was held on 15–16 November 2023, as an online meeting. Participants included the invited experts, all members of the working group, SAPEA representatives, the Group of Chief Scientific Advisors, and staff of the European Commission.

The workshop format was as follows:

- At the beginning of each workshop day, SAPEA and the Advisors provided an introduction to the Scientific Advice Mechanism, the topic and the background to the request.
- One working group member was in charge of moderating the talks and discussions for each day. The invited experts presented evidence about the impact of AI on scientific areas and the scientific process.
- Each talk was followed by questions and the day ended with a general discussion between all participants.

The content of each presentation, the opinions shared by the experts and the discussions are summarised below. The names of all participants can be found at the end of this report, along with the workshop programme.

The evidence presented and discussed will directly inform the SAPEA evidence review report on the same topic available on the website², and the Scientific Advice Mechanism's advice to the European Commission.

¹ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-07/Scoping_paper_AI.pdf

² <https://scientificadvice.eu/advice/artificial-intelligence-in-science/>

Context and scope

The Group of Chief Scientific Advisors provides independent scientific advice to the European Commission. The Advisors work closely with the SAPEA consortium, which conducts comprehensive reviews of the evidence.

The scoping paper for *Successful and timely uptake of AI in science in the EU* sets out the formal request for advice from the European College of Commissioners to the Group of Chief Scientific Advisors.

The evidence review report by SAPEA synthesises the evidence, in response to the main question from the scoping paper:

How can the European Commission accelerate a responsible uptake of AI in science (including providing access to high quality AI, respecting European Values) in order to boost the EU's innovation and prosperity, strengthen the EU's position in science and ultimately contribute to solving Europe's societal challenges?

The workshop on Key Area 2: Scientific Process, aimed to gather evidence to answer the questions set out in the scoping paper, under this key area:

- What is the impact of AI on the scientific process in your area of expertise, and its potential to re-shape science and its governance practices?
- What is the impact (positive and negative) of AI on everyday scientific practice and workflow in your area of expertise?
- Explore gaps, potential risks, workflows and checks that could be put in practice in your area of expertise.

Workshop report

Impact of AI on computer sciences

AI is a disruptive technology with the potential to replace human activities that involve decision-making, image recognition, natural language dialogue, planning, and learning. Humanity is at the beginning of the AI age and there are already several aspects of science affected including hypothesis generation, experiment design, data analysis, and prediction. Summarised below are the key themes where AI may impact computer science.

Accelerating discovery

With the ability to process vast amounts of data and identify patterns that would be impossible for humans to discern, AI is enabling researchers to make connections and develop insights that would otherwise take years, if not decades to uncover. Development of new algorithms and models that can even outperform human-designed approaches.

Bottom-up data-driven approach

In a top-down approach, scientists develop algorithms and models based on understanding the problem and then testing the hypotheses against real-world data. On the contrary, the bottom-up approach uses machine learning algorithms to analyse data and identify patterns, allowing the data to guide the understanding of the problem. This shift towards bottom-up data-driven research has the potential to revolutionise the field of computer science, as it allows researchers to tackle problems that were previously considered intractable.

Democratisation of computer science research

As AI tools and platforms become more accessible and user-friendly, researchers from a wide range of disciplines are able to leverage the power of AI to tackle problems in their own fields. A new era of interdisciplinary research, in which computer scientists collaborate easily with experts in fields, such as biology, chemistry, and physics to develop innovative solutions to complex problems.

In addition to the general applications, AI will certainly have field-specific impact in many computer science research areas.

Cybersecurity

AI can help identify potential threats and data breaches in real time and also provide the necessary solutions to avoid those issues. It can also help in protecting user identity and datasets. By automating time-consuming and repetitive tasks in real time, AI allows for monitoring and analysing behaviour patterns, predicting the outcomes of unusual behaviour, preventing bad actions and outcomes, taking preventive actions, and generating alerts of suspicious behaviours for human review in a record time. While cybercriminals often use AI for their own purposes, including creating new malware and hacking tools, automating phishing attacks, searching for loopholes in security, and using deepfake technology and malicious bots to impersonate people, AI enables us to fight back better.

Software engineering

AI tools can be used to predict system overloads, anticipate user behaviour, and optimise the user experience. The platforms that run and dispatch AI codes, AI can change and update code to meet minimum requirements. AI can also automate different tasks in software engineering, such as AI-based analysis for the deployment planning of development teams, computation of source code complexity, technical faults and software quality, approaches for the transformation of legacy systems and vendor steering, identification of duplicates and clones, risk and failure analysis, and benchmarking. The integration of large language models (LLMs) into software engineering practices offers significant benefits, including streamlined workflows, improved accuracy, reduced manual effort, and enhance team collaboration in the software development lifecycle. However, LLMs are designed to assist humans and not replace them, therefore domain-specific knowledge remains essential for achieving optimal results.

Quantum computing

Quantum computers can process a vast number of possibilities simultaneously. This could potentially speed up AI algorithms and process larger datasets more efficiently, leading to more powerful AI models. However, quantum computing requires entirely new algorithms and they are exceptionally difficult to develop.

Computer science education

Traditional classroom learning complemented with AI-driven tools and platforms offers personalised learning experiences. AI algorithms analyse students' learning patterns, identify their strengths and weaknesses, and subsequently tailor the curriculum to their needs. LLMs can be used to provide assistance and feedback to learners, help identify errors, suggest improvements, and provide explanations for code snippets. LLMs can be integrated into interactive learning platforms, allowing students to ask questions, seek explanations, and receive instant feedback. Grading assignments in computer science can certainly be automated with AI because AI is capable of analysing code, providing feedback, and assigning grades based on predefined criteria.

Impact of AI on data science

Data science is a new field, at the intersection between computing science, especially data management, mathematics and statistics, and some other scientific, industrial, or social domain where the data is coming from. As a field, data science heavily relies on AI and machine learning algorithms. There are three main stages in a data science pipeline:

1. data preparation: data curation, cleaning, wrangling
2. model development and deployment
3. data inference and visualisation

The first two stages are time-consuming and occur offline periodically, while the third stage is fast and occurs online on demand.

AI can support all three stages. For instance:

1. in finding the right data format (wrangling) (Braun et al, 2018; Furche et al, 2016; Sutton et al, 2018), or identifying outliers or low-quality data (cleaning) (Chu et al, 2016; Gudivada et al, 2017; Ilyas & Rekatsinas, 2022)
2. of course, in the core process of machine learning (modelling)
3. in choosing the right visualisation (Leban et al, 2006; Ropinski et al, 2017)

Data management systems, such as traditional relational database systems or other NoSQL types, include a suite of diverse components and tools to design, ingest, store, organise, process, and analyse data, as well as serve queries or other requests on the data and present the corresponding results and responses. Every component of a data management system can benefit from AI, such as in increasing the effectiveness of query optimisation for better reliability in the results. Current query optimisers struggle when dealing with large or complicated queries due to poor size and cost estimates (Leis et al, 2015), (Leis et al, 2015), but evidence shows that machine learning-based estimation could offer large improvements of these systems (Kraska et al, 2018; Marcus et al, 2021; Yang et al, 2019). As another example, data scientists use various tools to interact with, extract from, and analyse data from databases, often writing code in the SQL database language or general programming languages; AI can facilitate users so that they may perform some of these tasks more quickly and effectively by interacting with the system in higher-level languages, especially natural languages through prompt interfaces based on Large Language Models.

In the other direction, data science may also impact AI itself and influence the development of new relevant algorithms. For example, to optimise an LLM output, it is imperative to employ what is called Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG), where up-to-date customised data is injected into the inference process of the LLM.

Developing bottom-up AI requires large amounts of real-world data and, unfortunately, most of it is currently owned by big tech companies outside Europe. For data scientists and academic researchers to

excel, there is a need for European public and private sectors to create privacy-preserving European-based LLMs and make them available to all communities of interest.

Applications of AI to physics

There are four major paths in physics where AI plays a crucial role at every step of the scientific process (Krenn et al, 2022). These include automated idea generation from the literature, AI-driven experimental design, advanced experimental control, and discovering from experimental data.

AI to generate new ideas

Scientists have shown that it is possible to use millions of scientific papers to find new properties of materials that have never been described before. For example, when material science researchers used a text encoder from a literature review in a virtual high-dimensional search space, they found materials with similar properties clustered together (Tshitoyan et al, 2019). Using this method for 3 million scientific papers on thermoelectric materials, the scientists show that many of the known thermoelectric materials come up in this abstract space. Interestingly, materials that have never been described or measured to be thermoelectric are also present, suggesting new materials potentially have thermoelectric properties.

Additionally, physicists generate new ideas by using large knowledge networks that can be generated automatically from data (Krenn & Zeilinger, 2020). Using hundreds of thousands of past scientific publications, it is possible to build a knowledge representation of the field that evolves over time. Using this evolving knowledge network, it is then possible to evaluate the prospects of research areas and predict future trends about areas that will dominate. Funding mechanisms in North America have dedicated large funding for this strategy³.

AI-driven experimental design

Many experiments in physics first need simulations because doing an actual experiment is expensive and difficult. Physicists can devise a vast number of possible experiment setups and only a handful of those could be relevant and useful. With AI, scientists explore potential experimental designs, including quantum experiments (Krenn et al, 2020; Krenn et al, 2023; Krenn et al, 2016), photonic structure design (Sapra et al, 2020), topological material design (Peano et al, 2021), and many more (Brandstetter et al, 2022; Carleo & Troyer, 2017). AI can speed up simulators making experimental setup faster. For example, many physical simulators are now partly or completely replaced by much faster neural network-based simulators or high-performance computational methods (such as auto-differentiation) invented by the machine learning community (Rodríguez et al, 2023).

³ Schmidt Family Foundation, Advancing Science through Multi-Disciplinary AI <https://www.schmidtfutures.com/second-cohort-of-ai2050-senior-fellows-named-by-schmidt-futures/>; and the DARPA programme Announcement for Artificial Intelligence Exploration <https://sam.gov/opp/96835b0357344816bb1166533e56175e/view>

Advanced experimental control

Physics experiments are complex and traditionally scientists use hard-coded algorithms to control their experiments. AI systems use reinforcement learning to learn and control the experimental system automatically. The tokamak plasma for nuclear fusion control (Degraeve et al, 2022), the control and manipulation of quantum systems (Reuer et al, 2023), and the calibration of scaled-up experiments in quantum computers (Ares, 2021) are recent examples of AI-controlled experimentations.

Discoveries from experimental data

AI is discovering new knowledge from experimental data (Karagiorgi et al, 2022). For example, researchers identified new exoplanets in the habitable zone data collected by the Kepler telescope using an AI-based algorithm (Schölkopf et al, 2016). Scientists are training AI algorithms to explore subtle signals in the mega dataset from the Laser Interferometer Gravitational-Wave Observatory (LIGO) to discover gravitational waves (Cuoco et al, 2021). With AI, engineers are also improving the resolution of imaging systems, such as telescopes, microscopes, and electron scanning microscopes (Kalinin et al, 2022).

While AI has many benefits, it is not without limitations. AI methods that are not transparent make it challenging to interpret results. While AI allows scientists to explore new patterns, or extract new concepts and principles (Cranmer et al, 2020; Iten et al, 2020; Krenn et al, 2021; Liu & Tegmark, 2022), it is challenging to quickly verify the accuracy of many new AI-derived concepts.

Applications of AI to life sciences

AI is becoming a powerful tool in all life sciences and medical research areas. Biologists constantly produce big data stemming from cutting-edge new methodologies in sequencing, gene editing, and disease databases. With the field overwhelmingly embracing data-driven approaches in research, AI has a tremendous potential in solving problems in nanotechnology, climate change, agriculture, and medicine.

Success stories

Among the numerous examples of AI applications in life sciences, AlphaFold is probably the most talked about. AlphaFold developed by DeepMind predicts the 3D structures of thousands of proteins with more than 90% accuracy⁴ (Alderson et al, 2023; Huang et al, 2023). AI is helping design more efficient mRNA therapeutics⁵. In large sequencing databases, such as the Human Genome project⁶, AI and machine learning algorithms allow scientists to discover genetic alterations (Alharbi & Rashid, 2022), design new modified organisms, and discover new therapies (Drew, 2023; Lewis, 2023).

⁴ <https://phys.org/news/2023-11-powerful-ai-tool-gain-insights.html>

⁵ <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-023-01487-y>

⁶ <https://www.genome.gov/human-genome-project>

Despite the importance, many researchers warn against current trends of overconfidence in AI, demanding quality checks for data and results and addressing bias in training data (Hutson, 2020; Mitchell, 2023; Rudin, 2019; Sejnowski, 2020). These include developing new protocols and systems for comprehensive quality assessment, adopting interdisciplinary collaboration and training, and seeking new machine learning classifications based on the species, such as plants, microbes, animals, etc. Further, overconfidence in AI along with the lack of public regulation can contribute to misinformation.

The way ahead

There needs to be a common framework to bridge intellectual property and data ownership disparities between different research areas. By adopting Open and FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) practices, embracing collaborations and data sharing, combining datasets, biologists can make important discoveries using AI.

Applications of AI in social sciences

AI is reshaping sciences and social sciences in many ways (Togelius & Yannakakis, 2023). For example, to search for the best candidate in the social sciences hiring process, scientists first design a questionnaire, gather data, and fit a parametric model-based on the responses to come up with job recommendations (Bied et al, 2023). Using AI, this data-driven approach is feasible and faster. However, one caveat remains with this approach that might use a faulty surrogate measure to reflect the job seeker's qualifications.

The traditional methodology in social science includes understanding an issue first, then formulating laws, followed by making and testing predictions, which is a much longer process. With AI, this scientific process is reversed where the scientists infer laws directly from the data, however, this approach is overpowered by bias in data that will only reveal partial truth.

There are risks associated with using AI in social sciences. AI allows scientists to make predictions, but models can be inefficient at making predictions if they heavily rely on correlations. Depending on the data quality, correlation-based models can be very weak, making the results untrustworthy.

A second risk is that algorithms can decrease diversity. The 'winner takes all' paradigm can be potentially harmful. For example, researchers have shown that data-driven recommendations can lead to a congestion of the job market, where a fraction of job ads are recommended to job seekers, while a large fraction are never shown to job seekers. The overall perception is that there seem to be fewer job ads than actually exist.

Some models are potentially very harmful models that perpetuate existing data biases, such as gender-based prejudices. These are evident in salary gaps between men and women. Using AI to assess the bias reveals AI models mirror the existing wage disparities. Can AI be useful to prevent bias? Removing gender-related data to curb bias jeopardises AI's accuracy, posing a dilemma in balancing fairness and functionality.

Social scientists need to address whether they must acknowledge gender-specific preferences with the risk of embedding societal biases in the model or discard individual preferences to mitigate biases.

Applications of AI to economics

In the past 10 years, AI has evolved quickly, in particular with the development of LLMs, thus pushing the productivity frontier. AI has the potential to exacerbate some societal issues as well as pose security threats. According to the Bletchley Declaration⁷, AI has already been deployed across many domains of daily life including housing, employment, transport, education, health, accessibility, and justice, however, also posing significant risks without accountability, fairness, and human oversight. Some sectors of the economy where biased AI can cause significant societal harm⁸ include finance, banking, and insurance.

In the economy and beyond, there are threats of failing to implement AI in due time, missing the productivity frontier will bring threats of underdevelopment of AI tools, and losing industrial competitive edge. Moreover, threats brought by those developing AI for illegal or immoral purposes, such as the use of AI for the generation of false news by bad actors through deepfake technology, can destabilise nations. Failing to plan in advance for the creation of a workforce able to develop, manufacture, operate, and maintain AI tools may harm economies as the development of such skills can take years and the nations that do not invest in skilled workforce training programmes will be left behind in the new productivity frontier brought by AI tools. In this respect, the EU seems to be less prepared compared with the investments made by other international stakeholders.

In manufacturing, further AI deployment could add between \$200 to \$340 billion in value and contribute to improving the design of manufactured products, logistics, and maintenance⁹. This is currently a significant opportunity. In the finance and insurance industries, AI could be used to derive better regulations and to better enforce the regulations in the financial markets. AI is able to improve market predictions, help banking investments, and control financial assets, such as reducing defaults on loans (Cao, 2020). However, individuals may also be able to destabilise the economy through nefarious uses of AI. For example, the most disadvantaged insured risk becoming even more disadvantaged, and similarly, smaller insurers may become extinct in the insurance industry¹⁰.

⁷ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/ai-safety-summit-2023-the-bletchley-declaration>

⁸ The White House. Executive Order on the Safe, Secure, and Trustworthy Development and Use of Artificial Intelligence. October 30, 2023, USA. <https://www.whitehouse.gov/briefing-room/presidential-actions/2023/10/30/executive-order-on-the-safe-secure-and-trustworthy-development-and-use-of-artificial-intelligence/>

⁹ MGI 2023. [The economic potential of generative AI: The next productivity frontier](#). June 14, 2023, Report by The McKinsey Global Institute

¹⁰ Carlo Giovine, Larry Lerner, Jared Moon, and Stefan Schorsch, [Been there, doing that: How corporate and investment banks are tackling gen AI](#). McKinsey, Sep 25, 2023; Philippa Wain, Imran Rahman-Jones, [AI bot capable of insider trading and lying, say researchers](#), Nov 3, 2023, BBC News.

As data is dynamic, AI tools must be retrained periodically. Tools trained a few years ago might quickly become obsolete if not retrained. The rate of error of AI tools inevitably increases in time, hence, their value will also decrease over time if not periodically retrained (Valavi et al, 2022).

In the workforce, one may expect social tensions, with a reduction of the workforce in some domains and the advent of new domains that will lack a supply of workers. Probably, new professions will appear, such as AI trainers or LLM engineers. These professionals are similar to data analysts but will be specialised in the suitability of data for specific tasks to be automated. One way forward is augmentative human-AI relationship, instead of replacement, which may also provide advantages to automation in issues of fairness (Teodorescu et al, 2021).

Some of the main areas of socio-economic outcomes where AI fairness may cause concerns include housing, hiring, educational opportunities, and the court system (Mehrabi et al, 2019; Morse et al, 2022). In the United States legal framework, algorithms should make clear choices to avoid discrimination based on individual protected attributes, such as race, religion, national origin, gender, marital status, age, and socioeconomic status. The only federal law in the United States that currently defines and uses the concept of fairness is the Equal Credit Opportunity Act ¹¹. The European Union has advanced the initiative to legislate liability for harmful AI¹². Another example of recent legislative advances in AI fairness is the New York City AI Bias law on automated employment decision tools implemented in 2022¹³.

AI has been used a lot in hiring. Some companies rely on automated hiring interviews based on videos, which classify whether a person is hireable. There is a lot of literature on bias in hiring using algorithms that are now becoming of interest in both economics and computer science. Researchers using questionnaires and audio and video interviews attempted to identify biases that graders might have before they labelled the training set and to take out the bias before the data was fed to the machine learning too (Teodorescu et al, 2022). We need to dig deeper into the differences between backgrounds, such as the education of graders, when used in hiring applications.

Impact of AI on health sciences and medicine

In 2015, there were only 5 AI-supported medical devices approved by the United States Food and Drug Administration (USFDA). That number reached over 255 devices in 2022 with the vast majority of them used in radiology, cardiology, neurology, and ophthalmology (Muehlematter et al, 2021).

AI tools offer huge benefits in health by combining knowledge from natural sciences, physics, engineering, and other sciences. For example, researchers use magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) data to detect dementia at early stages using computer vision systems, physics, and physiology fundamentals (Nemy et al, 2023). AlphaFold, the AI algorithm predicting 3D protein structure, unravelled structures of thousands of

¹¹ <https://www.ftc.gov/legal-library/browse/statutes/equal-credit-opportunity-act>

¹² <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/european-approach-artificial-intelligence>

¹³ <https://www.nyc.gov/assets/dca/downloads/pdf/about/DCWP-AEDT-FAQ.pdf>

proteins in less than two years. These structures are key to supporting the development of new medical solutions, such as vaccines and precision medicine. AlphaFold combines knowledge from constructing deep neural networks, along with protein physics, geometry, and evolution (Callaway, 2022). Other applications of AI in medical sciences include the development of exoskeletons that help paralysed patients regain their ability to walk (Hachem et al, 2023; Wagner et al, 2018). Researchers use non-invasive brain-computer interface, prosthetics, electrode implants, and computer chips to develop algorithms for capturing neural activity to generate limb movement in patients (Chandrabhatla et al, 2023; Gupta et al, 2023).

The quality of input data and outputs, and the personal data protection issues are the main risks related to the AI application in health. Tools supporting medical sciences require enormous amounts of high-quality input data in compliance with current standards, such as HL7 Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources¹⁴. It is critical to be cognizant of potential bias in data monitoring. Further, transparency is essential to determine output quality, especially in device approval processes and in the AI tool validity. Finally, personal data protection relies on the active participation of each individual patient. The meaning of personal data is changing quickly, therefore, there is a need for extensive continuous communication with patients and the general public.

Impact of AI on engineering (modelling)

Smart cities are a great example of the impact of AI on engineering and in particular modelling. Smart cities rely on autonomous systems to provide services to citizens. These services include intelligent systems for transport, health, education, energy, etc. The main AI-based technologies required to run these cities include big data, the Internet of Things, 5G networks, and edge computing.

Simulating smart cities

AI can support literature reviews to identify knowledge gaps, formulate research problems, and suggest new questions. Integrated AI tools also provide additional computational tools in smart city research, such as built-in libraries, simulation software, and methods for implementing and designing new solutions. AI simulators facilitate the testing and evaluation of new methods and offer insight before deploying the products in real-life paradigms. However, heterogeneous data sources with unpredictable behaviours need monitoring before streamlining them for simulators.

Public awareness

Like AI applications in other research fields, AI in smart cities research needs to address issues related to bias (Manyika et al, 2019), ethics, reproducibility, transparency, and interpretability (Wang et al, 2023). Smart cities research impacts human societies directly, therefore, teaching the general public about the services needs to be part of the process design. The goal is to raise awareness about the impacts of AI on the end

¹⁴ <https://www.hl7.org/fhir/overview.html>

users by systematically engaging them in how the system works (Wang et al, 2019; Xu et al, 2021). Moreover, continuous education about the process and tools and how to use them properly can be mandated for developers and users at all stages of their careers to continue updating their knowledge (Chen et al, 2020; Somasundaram et al, 2020).

Impact of AI on engineering (automation and robotics)

Robotics and automation research have witnessed a complete transformation with AI (Ahn et al, 2022). Robotic systems are crucial in modern human society with their use in semi-autonomous vehicles in hazardous, subterranean settings, invasive surgical systems, and autonomous vehicles in different industries. All these systems require well-tuned controllers that are trained with AI systems¹⁵ (Tranzatto et al, 2022).

There are several LLMs with important roles in robotics and automation. For example, language and vision-language models show increased reasoning abilities through an inner monolog, supporting object manipulation (Driess et al, 2023; Huang et al, 2022) and navigation (Shah et al, 2022). Transformer models use input from text and images to output actions for robotic hands. Such LLMs allow for processing image data to acquire more robust and more generalizable behaviours (Padalkar et al, 2023). Many LLMs query pre-trained models to produce code and offer coding interfaces for programming complex robotic behaviours (Liang et al, 2023; Singh et al, 2023). These methods still heavily rely on prompt engineering for specific tasks and are not yet effective in complex applications.

Models in robotics have reinforcement learning where they learn which actions are good and which are bad (Kwon et al, 2023; Ma et al, 2023). While AI models learn these values, they still require critical human input due to the inherent real-world uncertainties (Ren et al, 2023). For example, operating robots in large offices or homes using AI remains a complex task that requires an AI tool to respecify and relearn actions into an executable plan (Chalvatzaki et al, 2023; Rana et al, 2023).

Moreover, standardisation and safety checks are required for new, emerging applications deployed in society. Adequate standardisation, along with transparency and responsible system, design will underlie trust and reliability in societal applications of these technologies. Interdisciplinary collaborations among technologists, ethicists, sociologists, and economists to design and implement transparent robotic systems showing trust and reliability for societal applications should be at the forefront. There must also be rigorous testing standards with certification from IEEE¹⁶ and ISO¹⁷ for collaborative and assistive robots¹⁸.

Ethics and accountability concerns are important risks in the development and deployment of AI in robotics. For example, human-robot interactions have important socio-ethical implications that should be monitored for their impact on society, such as job displacement, changes in skill requirements, and broader societal

¹⁵ <https://bostondynamics.com/atlas/>

¹⁶ Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers

¹⁷ International Organisation for Standardisation

¹⁸ <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#iso:std:iso:ts:15066:ed-1:v1:en>

shifts. Similar to Asilomar AI Principles¹⁹, an EU-wide tailored ethical and legal framework is needed specifically for the applications of AI in robotics.

Impact of AI in the humanities and digital humanities

What are digital humanities?

Digital humanities is an umbrella discipline encompassing computer science, art history, archaeology, linguistics, and several other humanities subjects (Ciula et al, 2018). The field existed for more than a decade where humanities researchers incorporated AI and machine learning algorithms into their studies. For example, art historians routinely use the computational linguistics method, Natural Language Processing (NLP).

Despite the use of computational methodologies in their work, many researchers feel overwhelmed by the advancements in digital humanities in the last 2–3 years. They are concerned about AI tools and how they impact humanities research.

The Cultural Values of AI Toolkit

The text-based AI system ChatGPT, the European open-source text-to-image AI Stable Diffusion, and the picture generators AI tools like DALL-E are revolutionary algorithms that can profoundly affect humanities research. With these AI tools, predictably, there is a discussion about what students learn in humanities and how they can falsify information. Moreover, digital humanities disciplines, like social sciences, need to tackle societal and cultural challenges centred around bias, diversity, and ethics in the training datasets (Offert & Bell, 2021). Therefore, the use of AI in digital humanities opens up concerns about its impact on culture and society. For example, Time Machine Europe is a mega project that aims to enliven Europe's rich past with digital technologies to create a comprehensive map of the European economic, social, cultural and geographical evolution across time (Kaplan & di Lenardo, 2017). By bringing cultural heritage and machine learning together to simulate large data of the past, this digital humanities project addresses what European values are and how problematic some of them can be.

Qualitative vs quantitative

Research in humanities is different from that in digital humanities. A key difference is that traditional humanists work qualitatively on scant data, whereas digital humanities researchers work on big data, such as 2 million images for quantitative analysis (Gefen et al, 2020). In that instance, AI offers an opportunity to bridge the gap between qualitative and quantitative research in humanities. While this is exciting, heterogeneous data is a common challenge. Despite having some standards, datasets in humanities are

¹⁹ <https://futureoflife.org/open-letter/ai-principles/>

widespread making it very difficult to train on different cultural heritages at the same time. While AI can have a cultural memory with the knowledge of time and diversity in cultures globally, bias is an important transdisciplinary challenge (Offert & Bell, 2021).

Computational social sciences and representation in Natural Language Processing

How the developments in AI impact the field of AI itself is an important topic that requires thorough discussion. How academics and private players will share and control infrastructure, research questions, and safeguarding scientific integrity is at the heart of this conversation.

The commercialisation happened too fast

While research trends that showed the growth of LLMs in the last two years were not surprising (Brants et al, 2007), experts didn't expect the unprecedented speed at which commercial LLMs affect everything. Particularly, the emergence of a new industry that sells state-of-the-art LLMs as a paid per access service was unexpected, forcing a major paradigm shift in the NLP research (Kaplan et al, 2020).

Scaling

One of the consequences is an unequal access where 90% of researchers have access to less than 10% of the available computing power, limiting their ability to train, further develop, and test competitive models. With a few paid services monopolising LLMs, academics will depend on them while losing infrastructure control at scale (Lee et al, 2023).

Benchmarking

Academic reviewers are increasingly asking researchers to benchmark their work using ChatGPT to validate the performance of their models before publishing on any methodological innovations. This results in unforeseen research costs in current funding schemes. For every research dataset with a usual size of about 100,000 sentences, a simple run of one model configuration for sentiment analysis or logical inference would cost several hundred euros. It is unclear at the moment if a European academic research affiliate should pay to access a private American company product (i.e. ChatGPT by OpenAI), and this way even provide the private sector more training data to further improve its LLMs, increasing the gap between academic and industry research even more.

Another major benchmarking concern is that researchers don't always know whether they are testing the right criteria and evaluating them appropriately due to a shortage of holistic large-scale human test sets (and mechanisms to produce those in academia). For example, when researchers report their model's

[accuracy and performance at 90%, it is often unclear whether that is comparable to a human solving a logical question or the model is simply overfitting on all the available evaluation (test) data.

Shortage of data sources

Test data is a main requirement to continue improving LLM performance. Researchers are yet unclear about how well the LLMs perform on real-world data because they simply can't keep up with providing the evaluation data at scale fast enough (Villalobos et al, 2022). To avoid overfitting problems, AI researchers predetermine specific metrics to train their data. However, as the chosen metrics become the goal, it becomes imperative to think about what future evaluation pipelines should look like.

Human evaluation (validating model performance by people) is a crucial part of NLP evaluation pipelines. Unfortunately, academics have lost control over human evaluation with LLMs. One key reason for this is that academia does not have scalable pipelines as the industry does (Ahmed et al, 2023). Therefore, academic researchers don't have access to large-scale human feedback, reinforcement learning, and human plausibility to test for AI safety, ethics, and social bias at scale (Casper et al, 2023).

Academics typically use crowdsourcing platforms or students for evaluation, however, they lack cross-disciplinary representation for large-scale evaluation. Researchers are also alert about a recent trend in surveys and crowdsourcing evaluations that are unusable because the crowdsourcing workers often use ChatGPT for summary instead of a person creating summaries as required for the human evaluation (Veselovsky et al, 2023). In addition to losing control over human-led benchmarking, the researchers are also seeing a dramatic decrease in collaborative public datasets. For example, as the popularity of commercial LLMs like ChatGPT rises, contributions to public platforms like Wikipedia, Stack Overflow, etc. continues to decline (del Rio-Chanona et al, 2023). This further motivates people to use AI products as a source of information. In the near short-term, there will be fewer input data available to train models, making the LLMs themselves as a main source of information, further amplifying the bias that already exists.

Identity crisis in research

Typically, every academic group drives its research on a limited set of questions fairly independently. With burgeoning growth in LLM service providers, there is a major identity crisis in the NLP field. For example, the LLM growth follows Moore's Law, where the field moved from 1 billion models to 500 billion models with increasing performance in the last two years. While this allows researchers to solve a large number of NLP tasks, they need to reckon with what kind of research questions the AI academics should focus on (Ignat et al, 2023; Li et al, 2023; Saphra et al, 2023; Togelius & Yannakakis, 2023).

In a world where everything is owned and solved by the industry, the real question for the field is to decide: What is the role of academia in AI? They further ought to ask more pertinent questions and look for new directives, such as:

- Should researchers be working on building better LLMs?

- Should researchers be working on trying to explain these current models and reverse engineer them to look for safety and bias issues?
- Should researchers be working on models developed by the industry and use them for socially desirable applications that the industry is necessarily not prioritising?
- Should researchers try to look for research areas that are farthest from the LLMs like working on niche domains or low-resource languages?

In summary, there needs to be a transdisciplinary discussion about how to scale academic AI infrastructure to drive progress in AI by the academic community.

Epistemology of AI in science

Epistemology is a field of studies concerned with what knowledge is and how humans generate knowledge. There are emerging epistemological debates related to AI. In this instance, AI is both the area of investigation and the tool to do the research. Therefore, researchers in epistemology and the philosophy of science discuss the methodological underpinnings of AI and its ethical considerations.

Is there a need for AI epistemology?

Scientific tools are not neutral from an epistemic perspective because some tools are better or worse based on the type of scientific question being studied. Additionally, scientific tools can be technical artefacts carrying and promoting different ethical values. Similarly, scientists need to think about why AI tools are used, how good they are for humans, and what financial, environmental, and other costs they will incur to do good (Russo et al, 2023). To include ethics in epistemology, AI can be investigated as a modelling process akin to model building in economics, sociology, and physics, allowing for asking value-based questions at each stage of the process and making recommendations based on that for trustworthy and sustainable AI.

Transparency

An epistemological question relates to transparency. Because many algorithmic procedures are opaque, there is a debate about to what extent researchers can explain any phenomena coming from opaque models (Burrell, 2016). Similarly, should non-transparent models themselves be acceptable or not. In recent years, epistemologists are asking specific questions about transparency looking to address whether transparency is required at all or for whom the process should be transparent. The key argument behind these questions is that a robust modelling process makes results acceptable, therefore obliterating transparency as a necessary ingredient of the models (Creel, 2020).

Algorithmic bias

Algorithmic bias is another epistemological issue. Bias in algorithms is a well-documented fact that resembles bias in human-made models. Therefore, from the technical and ethical perspective, how humans will handle bias in AI is a critical matter, especially in the fields such as counselling, human resources, and other (Simon et al, 2020).

AI in academic writing

With ChatGPT and other generative AI tools becoming commonplace, they are broadly affecting academic writing. Because these generative AI tools became available to the public rapidly and without any warning, it created several legal implications for academics. For example, the Springer publication house alerted researchers that as per the legal guidelines of authorship compliance, the publisher will not consider ChatGPT and other generative AI tools as authors on academic manuscripts. Elsevier also developed ethical guidelines specific to the use of generative AI, where authors should for example disclose the use of generative AI in their manuscripts and where AI cannot be listed as author or co-author.²⁰

While the AI tools are not authors, researchers are increasingly using ChatGPT in their work, making AI's contribution significant in academic writing. For epistemologists, this demands rethinking of the concept of knowledge itself. With writing and knowledge coming from generative AI, academic reviewers also struggle to determine whether ChatGPT content in manuscripts is legal, legible, and ethical. While academics have clear guidelines about recognising and tackling plagiarism, they merely rely on ad hoc guidelines from their institutions instead of proper tools to detect AI writing. Researchers are however enthusiastic about the ongoing discussion everywhere on how to adapt teaching to incorporate challenges associated with AI writing as soon as possible (Friederich & Symons, 2023; Russo, 2023).

Sustainability of AI practices in science

With the AI and machine learning revolution in all sectors, including healthcare, finance, transportation, and education, it is high time to discuss its cost (Strubell et al, 2019). The models are getting more complex by day to achieve higher performance, consuming energy significantly to the point of contributing to a major carbon footprint. For example, training a single AI model could emit as much carbon as five cars in their lifetime²¹.

Moreover, most data, personal and industrial, are stored in a cloud that AI researchers access through cloud computing. Data centres hosting data and facilitating cloud computing consume a lot of electricity and

²⁰ <https://www.elsevier.com/about/policies-and-standards/publishing-ethics>

²¹ <https://www.technologyreview.com/2019/06/06/239031/training-a-single-ai-model-can-emit-as-much-carbon-as-five-cars-in-their-lifetimes/>

water. Models like ChatGPT are even more energy expensive with an estimated energy cost of one GPT-3 training session requiring the energy equivalent to 126 Danish homes in one year²².

The ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI by the European Union (EU) include societal and environmental well-being among the key seven requirements²³. According to the EU AI Act, the Parliament's priority is to make sure that AI systems in use in the EU are safe, transparent, non-discriminatory, and environmentally friendly (OECD, 2023; UNESCO, 2022)²⁴.

Green AI vs Red AI

Green AI refers to research that produces novel results while taking into account the computational cost (Schwartz et al, 2020). In contrast, Red AI refers to traditional AI research focused on improving the models aggressively using massive computational resources without considering the cost.

Green-by algorithms deal with developing applications in different sectors that contribute to sustainability and combating climate change. For example, a recent study assessed the role of AI in potentially solving all 17 goals and 169 targets recognized in the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (Vinuesa et al, 2020). Similarly, AI-based monitoring of water, energy, land use, and livestock health will optimise resource allocation at both local and global scales.

Algorithm optimisation

Green-in focuses on finding paths for scalable and sustainable algorithms to reduce the CO2 footprint of current algorithms (Anthony et al, 2020). Although at early stages, many algorithmic optimisation methods are already available for increasing model efficiency. One trick researchers use is to represent their data using less than 64 bits and use low precision arithmetic operations (Morán-Fernández et al, 2020). This not only reduces energy consumption but also allows researchers to execute algorithms on less power-consuming, smaller devices. Many researchers began to focus on hardware optimisation and working with efficient GPUs to make the computation more efficient.

The choice of data centres is a crucial part of Green AI. A data centre's carbon footprint is proportional to its efficiency and its location. If a choice is available, researchers should choose a data centre in a country with a lower carbon footprint.²⁵

Lastly, researchers can make smart decisions during the modelling process. For example, scientists can run the algorithms for a shorter time when the longer training time improves the model just a little. Several tools facilitate calculating the energy consumption of AI algorithms and help predict energy consumption even

²² https://www.theregister.com/2020/11/04/gpt3_carbon_footprint_estimate/

²³ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>

²⁴ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/european-approach-artificial-intelligence>

²⁵ https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/daviz/co2-emission-intensity-14/#tab-googlechartid_chart_41

before training their algorithm. If the algorithm consumes high energy, researchers can make further modifications to reduce the carbon footprint.

Example of AI in science research programmes

Researchers at Uppsala University in Sweden are developing a university-wide programme to use AI across all research disciplines encompassing 5000 researchers and 50,000 students. The goal of the project is to involve everyone in the University to use AI as a tool and study its impact in building an organisation and communities. The ongoing projects are in humanities and social sciences, medicine and pharmacy, and science and technology research areas.

For example, a project in medicine involves researchers testing either a person or an algorithm on an electrocardiogram exam and asking to deliver a prediction of an abnormal electrical activity. The algorithm reached a human-level performance on this task, making it a potential clinical diagnostic tool in future. Moreover, the algorithm discovered new patterns in myocardial infarction which are difficult to identify by a person (Gustafsson et al, 2022).

The University-wide programme includes other projects, such as machine learning quantum gravity and deep learning for high-energy neutrino astronomy in the Department of Physics and Astronomy, Self-driving labs for battery discovery in the Department of Chemistry, Assistive AI, disability and norms of being human in the Department of Informatics and Media, and AI tools to predict the risk of common diseases using genetic data in the Department of Immunology, Genetics, and Pathology. The researchers are now working to identify the effect of these individual projects on their research ecosystem.

Impact of AI in scientific publishing and communications

The increased popularity of generative AI in education and teaching practices raises many concerns for professionals in scientific publishing and communication. There are both advantages and disadvantages of incorporating AI in scholarly communication.

Positive impacts of AI

Generative AI has significantly improved language editing vastly benefiting non-native English speakers. AI models have also helped democratise and diversify science by improving accessibility, where non-scientific audiences can simply generate an easy-to-understand layman summary of a complex scientific manuscript. Additionally, AI makes it easy to understand the intricacies of the publishing system to newcomers like early career researchers in developing literature reviews, letters to an editor, publishing logistics, etc.

Negative impacts of AI

While advantageous in many aspects, generative AI is exacerbating the spread of misinformation by generating content that is not checked for accuracy. While AI improves accessibility, it can also increase the digital divide. For example, people who can afford and access premium AI models might benefit more from it, widening that digital divide. AI can also diminish skills and competencies if the researchers overly rely on them for all aspects of their academic work, including data analysis, literary review writing, research assessment, etc. and other research skills.

Plagiarism

Plagiarism is one of the obvious concerns, as AI's ability to synthesise and rephrase existing content makes it easy to plagiarise anything. Journal publishers use many tools to detect plagiarism, however, these software tools are not always good enough to recognise content plagiarised by AI. Moreover, AI can cause copyright and intellectual property infringement by using text and images from research papers that are copyrighted. Further, the lack of a comprehensive ethics framework in AI applications can lead to compromising ethical standards of scientific publishing.

Implicit bias

Implicit bias is another complication where the current pipelines of creating training sets are influencing research findings and citation practices. If AI is trained on data reflecting white male, western perspectives, one of its clear dangers is strengthening the hegemony of Western science while undermining work from the academics in the Global South. Predatory publishing is already a challenge in scholarly communication because predatory journals or paper mills create fraudulent content. Generative AI can essentially make it easy to create such content, inadvertently reinforcing existing biases and stifling promotion of diversity. Moreover, the lack of transparency and black box nature of AI systems in the decision-making process can introduce bias and obscurity, eroding trust in scientific findings (Flanagin et al, 2023).

Potential checks and recommendations

To alleviate implicit bias and plagiarism issues in academic publishing, there needs to be a massive overhaul in data sharing and governance frameworks. These guidelines should also include how to use data within generative AI applications, especially by demanding greater transparency for the AI models. Furthermore, ethical guidelines for authorship, credit, and potential research misconduct needs priority. It is imperative to determine them quickly with multiple publishers joining forces to create a framework for the community (Bockting et al, 2023).

These guidelines must ensure that AI applications align with the principles of responsible research and communication (Kaebnick et al, 2023). The community should create robust and transparent input platforms that embrace open access. There should also be increased engagement with AI technology providers seeking increased accountability for them. Further, banning AI as co-authors and clearly outlining how

authors used AI in research and writing must be a standard in fulfilling legal and moral responsibility (Hosseini et al, 2023). The ultimate goal of future policymaking should be distinguishing between using AI to improve content (acceptable) versus using AI to generate content (not acceptable).

Impacts of AI on copyright and intellectual property

There are three legal aspects of intellectual property rights impacted by AI, namely the use of protected works for scientific inputs, research exemptions, and the creation of scientific AI outputs.

Use of protected works

Scientific articles, images, and knowledge are intellectual property and AI systems typically train on these input data. Some input data are protected by copyright or intellectual property rights. In the third version of the AI act by the European Parliament, the AI providers are only obligated to document and disclose summary of the training data that is protected by copyright. Unfortunately, the summary is not enough to quote all the resources, papers, and outputs, making it challenging to assess copyright and patent protection (European Commission et al, 2020). At the same time the protected works are frequently used without any permission of their authors.

Text and data mining exemptions

There are two exemptions for text and data mining in European law. Under the Digital Single Market Directive - Article 3, research institutions are allowed to do text and data mining for scientific research purposes (Art. 3 Directive (EU) 2019/790). Another exemption applies on text and data mining for other than research purposes. However, there are many legal inconsistencies between EU member states with regard to the latter exemption. Therefore, AI researchers and service providers might need to indicate all the sources along with author profiles despite the exemptions depending on the member state (Margoni & Kretschmer, 2022).

AI-created outputs

A balance between AI-assisted output and AI-created output is another legal quandary. For any content, originality and creativity are attributed to the person making that content. The author can be only a physical person. In the legal system, the author is a creator for the content. With AI-created content, whether the AI system deployer or the user could be the author needs to be defined. Moreover, it is necessary to clarify whether the AI-created content is a copyrighted work at all. Additional discussion relates to patents. Under the patent laws, it is yet unclear who should be deemed an inventor if AI-created output becomes patentable (Picht & Thouvenin, 2023).

Impact of AI on peer review

Peer review assesses the originality, quality, and validity of research work by gathering experts' opinions and criticisms. AI has the potential to accelerate the peer review process by automating certain tasks, such as plagiarism checks, manuscript formatting, quality control for fraudulent and erroneous data, testing the validity of statistical tests, and many more. However, [AI cannot assess the novelty and validity of research findings better than researchers who are experts in their fields. Moreover, AI can introduce machine bias by focusing on authors instead of content.

Case study

A recent study tested the potential of AI in peer review by evaluating a large number of conference papers using an AI model (Checco et al, 2021). The researchers found that AI shows high impact and accuracy on plagiarism, paper formatting, and scope. While AI is somewhat useful in paper readability in English, it is unreliable in assessing rigour, novelty, and impact of research papers. Evaluating these key attributes still requires expert human review.

Is peer review perfect?

Before discussing the impact of AI on peer review, it is imperative to first discuss the flaws in the current peer review process. There is a deluge of publications in academia with nearly 250 million manuscripts already available and 5 million more added each year. It is becoming impossible to assess all of their quality and reproduce many results. Because AI will use many low-quality studies as training data, the knowledge it will represent will not be accurate. To improve peer review using AI, it is critical to first improve the scientific studies and organise them for better accessibility for AI applications.

Organising knowledge

The Knowledge Graph is a new way of organising scientific knowledge to easily extract domain-specific concepts which are otherwise hidden in the text of scientific publications²⁶. By organising them in a semantic database, users can find specific research questions with comprehensive answers summarised from different papers. Moreover, the database has better machine readability that can find expert peer reviewers based on the citation history and Google Scholar records.

Impact of AI on research assessment

Research assessment in academia focuses on the originality, rigour, and significance of the study (Langfeldt et al, 2020). Research quality is often misconstrued as long-term citation counts. While long-term citation counts can reflect on the research quality to an extent (Aksnes et al, 2019), a study's scientific impact cannot

²⁶ <https://orkg.org/>

always be measured by citation counts. For example, several high-quality, path breaking papers don't have high citation count and many low-quality papers are highly cited for various reasons. Therefore, peer or expert review is central to research quality evaluation.

How will AI impact research quality evaluations (Kousha & Thelwall, 2023)? In a case study, researchers used provisional peer review scores for thousands of articles in different research areas submitted to the UK Research Excellence Framework and trained AI models to evaluate research quality using the available peer review scores. This is the only large-scale study using AI to predict research quality scores for journal articles. Each research output used in the study was scored on a four-point scale given by field-specific experts. The UK Research Excellence Framework results are being used to assign £16 billion of research funding, which is why they used over 1000 experts to assign the scores. Research that scored less than 3-points is not being given any funds.

Assessing AI performance

Researchers in the above case study predicted individual paper's quality rating with AI using paper and journal citation rates, title text, keywords, and other quantifying measures. The researchers found that in arts, humanities, and social sciences papers, AI results underperformed with results similar to random guesswork. In natural health sciences, biological sciences, and economics, AI performed well but never showed more than 75% accuracy, which counts as poor ranking in many research areas. These results indicate that AI is not accurate in assessing research quality. According to many experts, it is almost impossible to have an accurate AI system because human reviewers have lifetime expertise in their research. In that regard, AI has a shallower knowledge (Thelwall et al, 2023).

While AI underperforms in scoring individual articles' accuracy, it shows improvements in assessing whole departments and schools on the basis of the average scores of their articles. However, the researchers detected bias at the department level, specifically against the higher-scoring departments. AI undervalued the higher-scoring departments and overvalued the lower-scoring departments, suggesting the algorithm might have a tendency to lean towards average quality for all departments.

Merging strengths of people and AI

Evaluators can adopt a strategy where they work with human reviewers and provide them AI predictions based on probabilities. The reviewers can incorporate AI-based information into their judgments based on stringent guidelines. While this could be a beneficial approach in post-publication quality evaluation, some EU guidelines might hinder its utility. For example, the EU is a signatory of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment²⁷, which recommends against using journal impact factor as a proxy for research quality check. Since AI will rely on such measures, there needs to be a special consideration for future strategies.

²⁷ <https://coara.eu/agreement/the-agreement-full-text/>

Challenges in grant review

AI models typically use citation and journal data to assess research papers, however, these metrics are not available for grant applications. Therefore, it is prudent to assume that AI will be less accurate in assessing their quality. However, probability predictions can still be useful where reviewers can reliably identify and remove weak submissions before they begin grant review.

In summary, it is unlikely that AI will replace human decision-making in research quality evaluation, but AI can be trained to augment human review processes and make review processes faster.

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Workshop methods

Expert selection

In the context of the request for Advice on the topic ‘Successful and timely uptake of Artificial Intelligence in science in the EU’ SAPEA issued a call for nominations on 18 July 2023, describing the scope, timeline and expertise required. The call for nominations was sent via the academy networks to their member academies, who were invited to nominate experts following the procedure described in the SAPEA Quality Assurance Guidelines²⁸. Experts involved in the workshop were selected from the list of nominees. Additional experts were also identified through desk research by the academy networks. The list of areas of expertise that should be covered in the workshop was established in coordination with the SAM Secretariat and the member of the SAPEA working group in charge of key area 2.

The experts were selected by SAPEA and the member of the working group in charge of key area 2 on the basis of scientific excellence and disciplinary requirements as a priority, taking into account commitment and time availability, and the criteria set out in our strategy of diversity and inclusiveness:

- inter- and multidisciplinary
- involvement in the wider scientific community;
- inclusion of early- and mid-career researchers
- gender balance
- wide geographical coverage, including from Widening countries

The final group of experts who attended the workshop included 50% of female experts. 25% of attending experts were early-career and 38% mid-career researchers. 30% of experts came from Widening Countries. The following countries were represented by the experts: Czechia, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, The Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, United Kingdom, USA.

Process

Experts received the scoping paper along with the questions posed in key area 2 in advance of the workshop. They were asked to present on the scientific topic of interest, related to their area of expertise. In line with the SAPEA principle of transparency, workshop expert participants were asked to declare any conflict of interest and any interest that might be perceived by SAPEA as a conflict of interest in relation to this scientific topic at the beginning of their presentations.

²⁸ SAPEA, Science Advice for Policy by European Academies. (2023). Quality assurance guidelines and procedures on science advice for policy and society. Berlin: SAPEA. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8329539>

Experts also received specific instructions about the format of presentations:

- listing the scientific publications cited in the presentations
- preparing the content of the presentation by drawing on their own research but also on their broad knowledge of the field
- keeping the confidentiality of participants until the publication of the report

The report summarising the workshop was prepared by SAPEA and sent to all experts present for feedback before publication. To encourage openness and the sharing of information, the public summary report was prepared in an anonymous, non-attributed style.

Workshop programme

Day 1, 15 November 2023

- 14:00: *Welcome and introduction to SAPEA*
- 14:10: *Background to the request*
- 14:20: *Introductory remarks*
- 14:25: *Impact of AI on computer sciences*
- 14:40: *Impact of AI on data science*
- 14:55: *Applications of AI to physics*
- 15:10: *Applications of AI to life sciences*
- 15:25: *Applications of AI to social sciences*
- 15:40: *Applications of AI to economics*
- 15:55: *Break*
- 16:10: *Impact of AI on health sciences and medicine*
- 16:25: *Impact of AI on engineering (modelling)*
- 16:40: *Impact of AI on engineering (automation and robotics)*
- 16:55: *General discussion*
- 17:25: *Wrap-up and conclusions*
- 17:30: *Next steps and closing*

Day 2, 16 November 2023

- 09:00: *Welcome and introduction to SAPEA*
- 09:10: *Background to the request*
- 09:20: *Introductory remarks*
- 09:25: *Impact of AI on humanities and digital humanities*
- 09:40: *Computational social sciences, representation in NLPs*
- 09:55: *Epistemology of AI in science*
- 10:10: *Sustainability of AI practices in science*

Workshop methods

- 10:40: Example of AI in science research programmes
- 10:55: Impact of AI on scientific publishing and communications
- 11:10: Impact of AI on copyright and intellectual property
- 11:25: Impact of AI on peer review
- 11:40: Impact of AI on research assessment
- *11:55: General discussion*
- *12:25: Wrap-up and conclusions*
- *12:30: Next steps and closing*

Scientific Advice Mechanism

to the European Commission

Successful and timely uptake of artificial intelligence in science in the EU

7 December 2023

People workshop report

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Introduction

Evidence-gathering expert workshops are a vital part of SAPEA's rapid evidence review process. Together with the literature reviews, they constitute the main avenue for evidence-gathering from the wider scientific community.

This evidence-gathering workshop for the topic *Successful and timely uptake of Artificial Intelligence in science in the EU* addressed Key Area 3 of the scoping paper¹: the impact of AI on people. It was held on 7 December 2023, as an online meeting. Participants included the invited experts, all members of the working group, SAPEA representatives, the Group of Chief Scientific Advisors and staff of the European Commission.

The workshop format was as follows:

- At the beginning of each workshop day, SAPEA and the Advisors provided an introduction to the Scientific Advice Mechanism, the topic and the background to the request.
- One working group member was in charge of moderating the talks and discussions for each day. The invited experts presented evidence about the impact of AI on education and careers of the scientists and researchers.
- Each talk was followed by questions and the day ended with a general discussion between all participants.

The content of each presentation, the opinions shared by the experts and the discussions are summarised below. The names of all participants can be found at the end of this report, along with the workshop programme.

The evidence presented and discussed will directly inform the SAPEA evidence review report on the same topic available on the website², and the Scientific Advice Mechanism's advice to the European Commission.

¹ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-07/Scoping_paper_AI.pdf

² <https://scientificadvice.eu/advice/artificial-intelligence-in-science/>

Context and scope

The Group of Chief Scientific Advisors provides independent scientific advice to the European Commission. The Advisors work closely with the SAPEA consortium, which conducts comprehensive reviews of the evidence.

The scoping paper for *Successful and timely uptake of AI in science in the EU* sets out the formal request for advice from the European College of Commissioners to the Group of Chief Scientific Advisors.

The evidence review report by SAPEA synthesises the evidence, in response to the main question from the scoping paper:

How can the European Commission accelerate a responsible uptake of AI in science (including providing access to high quality AI, respecting European Values) in order to boost the EU's innovation and prosperity, strengthen the EU's position in science and ultimately contribute to solving Europe's societal challenges?

The workshop on Key Area 3: People, aimed to gather evidence to answer the questions set out in the scoping paper, under this key area:

- Main question: How can the EU best prepare for the impact and requirements of AI on the education and careers of the scientists and researchers of today and tomorrow, and what skills and competencies should education policies prioritise in this context?
- Sub-question: What are ways to ensure that researchers (at all stages of their education and professional development) and organizations have sufficient knowledge on using AI in science (and on related skills such as IT and computing, statistics, data analytics) and affordable access to infrastructure, data, computing capacity and AI tools and technologies?
- Sub-question: Which scientific jobs carry a high risk of being outsourced to AI-based technology; and the impact of AI (taking over some of researchers' tasks) on scientific workforce and researchers' careers.

Workshop report

European AI infrastructure access and sharing

Access and sharing of AI infrastructure across Europe is explored through a national example: the Czech National Supercomputing Centre³. This example is then compared to the European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (EuroHPC)⁴, providing an overview of their operations.

National-level access

The Czech National Supercomputing Center was established in 2011. It operates two supercomputers (including Karolina) as well as other special systems. It plays three major roles:

- **Education:** through the Technical University of Ostrava, where they have training and educational activities in the field of AI, high performance data analysis, high performance computing and quantum computing
- **Research:** through the e-INFRA CZ⁵ network, which is a strategic research infrastructure that hosts 5 research laboratories
- **Provider:** providing national scientists with supercomputing technologies, data storage and corresponding services, video conference services, certification services and more. The Centre also operates internet in the country, which connects main universities and research centres

The centre has strong international collaborations. It is a member of the LUMI consortium,⁶ which operates the most powerful supercomputer in Europe (LUMI, in Finland), and takes part in many EU-wide initiatives for the sharing of computing infrastructure (e.g. EuroHPC JU, PRACE,⁷ EUDAT,⁸ ETP4HPC,⁹ BDVA,¹⁰ EOSC,¹¹ LUMI). The centre also has strong international collaborations through EU-funded projects and cooperates with the industry.

A third of the funding for the supercomputer Karolina comes from EuroHPC, which allows European researchers from academia, research institutes, public authorities and industry to apply for access. The main

³ <https://www.it4i.cz/en>

⁴ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/high-performance-computing-joint-undertaking>

⁵ <https://www.e-infra.cz/en>

⁶ <https://www.lumi-supercomputer.eu/lumi-consortium/>

⁷ <https://prace-ri.eu/>

⁸ <https://eudat.eu/>

⁹ <https://www.etp4hpc.eu/>

¹⁰ <https://www.bdva.eu/>

¹¹ <https://eosc-portal.eu/>

users are big national universities and research centres, institutes of the Czech Academy of Sciences, working predominantly in the field of material science, biosciences and engineering.

At national level, academic and research institutions as well as public organisations are eligible to access the centre's clusters across the country and given free access. There are different types of access possibilities depending on the needs (e.g. multi-year projects, fast and short-term access, or regular access as part of educational activities or contract research with private companies). Access is given to teams of researchers and not only to individuals. At the moment, the Centre counts more than 110 active projects focused on AI, a number that was multiplied by 10 within the past 10 to 15 years. Training is offered to users, with special courses on how to use the infrastructure efficiently.

In order to ensure that EU researchers have sufficient knowledge about these infrastructures and how to use them, it is key to communicate and disseminate the information. At the national level, this is done by recruiting staff within the centre, who are in charge of proactively liaising with the AI community. This way any key information (e.g. calls for applications) is disseminated widely.

EU-level access

EuroHPC is a joint undertaking which leads the way in European supercomputing. At the moment it includes 34 participating countries, the European Union represented by the European Commission and 3 private partners (a big data value association, a European quantum industry consortium and a European technology platform for HPC). The main goals of EuroHPC are to:

- develop, deploy, extend and maintain a world leading, supercomputing, quantum computing service and data infrastructure, ecosystem in Europe
- support the development of innovative supercomputing components, technologies, knowledge and applications to underpin a competitive European supply chain
- widen the use of HPC and quantum infrastructures to a large number of public and private users wherever they are located in Europe and supporting the development of key HPC skills for European science and industry

It is funded through the Digital Europe Programme,¹² the Horizon Europe programme¹³ and the Connecting Europe Facility.¹⁴

There are nine operational systems which are part of the EuroHPC supercomputers network (in Slovenia, Czechia, Bulgaria, Luxembourg, Finland, Italy, Portugal, Spain and Greece), three of which are among the largest supercomputers in the world. Other systems are underway in Germany and in France. Furthermore,

¹² <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/activities/digital-programme>

¹³ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe_en

¹⁴ <https://wayback.archive-it.org/12090/20221222151902/https://ec.europa.eu/inea/en/connecting-europe-facility>

the EuroHPC will also allow access to quantum computers within six institutions across Europe (in Spain, France, Italy, Germany, Czechia and Poland).

Academic and research institutions, public sector organisations, industrial enterprises and small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are eligible to access the EuroHPC supercomputers. Types of access are similar to national-level access. There are also conditions for access, which include acknowledging the use of the resources, contributing to dissemination events and submitting a report after completion of the resource allocation. So far, through this mechanism, almost 2 billion core hours were distributed, and the resources were mostly used for STEM sciences.

Major developments are underway, such as the upcoming second exascale computer hosted by the Jules Verne consortium in France¹⁵, or an ongoing call for a hosting entity and industrial consortium for an AI supercomputer. There is a new large AI Grand Challenge, AI-BOOST,¹⁶ a prominent open challenge prize programme that will serve as a standard for the European AI community.

It is also key to train researchers on how to use these infrastructures efficiently. Special training and tools are needed to acquire this skill, and many of them are now available e.g. in libraries. Training on both hardware and software is important.

How can the AI training of researchers and specialists be improved?

AI training for researchers and specialists is underway in many countries across Europe, and this section explores this landscape in Germany. Some key organisations in Germany, including the KI@SCHOOL project in Bavaria¹⁷, the Bavarian Research Institute for Digital Transformation¹⁸, the AI Campus¹⁹ (a German learning platform), and the German Informatics Society's section for AI²⁰, contribute to AI education, research, and the development of white paper reports.

Challenges in academic AI education

One of the primary challenges observed in AI research and education is the need for an adequate number of senior researchers and full professors with expertise in specific AI areas. A second significant challenge is the need to teach AI methods balancing breadth and depth in AI competencies and skills, covering diverse topics while incorporating interdisciplinary and ethical aspects.

¹⁵ https://eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/jules-verne-consortium-will-host-new-eurohpc-exascale-supercomputer-france-2023-06-20_en

¹⁶ <https://aiboost-project.eu/>

¹⁷ <https://www.bildungspakt-bayern.de/projekte-ki-at-school/>

¹⁸ <https://www.bidt.digital/>

¹⁹ <https://ki-campus.org/about?locale=en>

²⁰ <https://fb-ki.gi.de/en/>

In STEM education and research, challenges are the integration of machine learning and data science into STEM curricula, taking into account the often-limited background in statistics. The lack of knowledge and teaching of empirical research methods in computer science or in the STEM curricula risks hindering effective data collection and measurement in complex AI constructs.

In non-technical disciplines such as humanities or social sciences, it will be important to ensure that students and researchers understand AI's role as a subdiscipline of computer science, emphasising understanding of typical pitfalls of machine learning approaches such as overfitting to specific information in training data and unfair models due to sampling biases or historical biases in the data. Basic components of an AI curriculum should include heuristic search methods, knowledge-based approaches (representation and inference), machine learning (interpretable approaches, statistical approaches, deep learning architectures, and generative approaches), extended by interdisciplinary input and methods for human-centric and trustworthy AI (Schmid, 2023), explainable AI (XAI) (Bruckert et al, 2020; Rabold et al, 2019) methods (Schmid & Wrede, 2022), cognition (Göbel et al, 2022; Thaler & Schmid, 2021), human computer interaction (Schmid & Finzel, 2020), ethics, law.

Experience from Germany

In Germany, several initiatives are developed to address these challenges. The country has made significant investments in new professorships, particularly in machine learning, to meet the growing demand for AI specialists. However, due to the high demand for these positions, there is a risk of lack of supply of individuals with sufficient in-depth expertise, and a risk that AI data science in curricula cannibalises other core areas in computer science that are necessary for AI expertise (e.g. formal languages, algorithms and data structures). Germany has also funded specific graduate schools and postdoc programmes on AI.

There have been investments in the development of modules to introduce AI and data science topics in a wide range of study programmes outside computer sciences, for example the BMBF programme 'AI for University Education'²¹. However, to function properly, this requires training, education or experience in interdisciplinary collaboration, to understand other disciplines' core questions or methods. A second challenge is that including AI and data science modules in curricula might lead to the exclusion of some topics from the core curriculum, which is a very difficult question to address.

Germany also has an initiative called 'AI Campus'²², which provides broad, accessible AI courses and resources, promoting cross-institutional cooperation and addressing diverse educational needs. These resources are open source and used in many German-speaking countries in the EU, spanning from 'Explainable AI for Engineers' to 'Data Literacy for Primary Schools'.

²¹ [Learning from Learners – VoLL-KI Bamberg \(uni-bamberg.de\)](https://www.uni-bamberg.de/learning-from-learners)

²² <https://ki-campus.org/front>

Impact and requirements of AI on the education and careers of the scientists in the EU

To achieve this goal, the EU should find a unique European approach that aligns with the AI Strategy objective of making AI in education and research human-centric and trustworthy. Furthermore, it is crucial to involve national expert organisations, such as the section AI of the German Informatics Society and Germany's AI platform, along with experts from the European Association for Artificial Intelligence and CLAIRE²³, when designing curricula. Promoting Europe-wide cooperation in the field of AI skills and competencies, as well as AI tools, should be based on principles of cooperation and openness, including open source and open educational resources (OER). Rather than starting from scratch, efforts should identify existing resources that have successfully supported AI skills development in member states, such as the AI Campus in Germany²⁴. As a proactive measure, there could be the establishment of a European AI toolbox specifically designed for open-source AI tools in education and research.

Regarding skills and competencies that education policies should prioritise, a first identified need is the development of joint European standards for in depth AI and data science curricula to educate future AI researchers and experts. Secondly, incorporating a human-centric perspective in AI curricula seems essential. For the safe and competent use of AI tools in different domains, it will be critical to provide modules and teaching material that include basic understanding of general principles and methods of AI, raising awareness about pitfalls, how to detect them and avoid them, Finally, it will be essential to provide AI tools and education for a broad range of domains (e.g. medicine, engineering, humanities, journalism, teachers).

In terms of knowledge and skills development, free online courses on Artificial Intelligence in research (asynchronous learning) and free synchronous webinars on the same subject play a crucial role. Additionally, utilising existing Open Educational Resources (OER) material, particularly focused on AI in Higher Education, offers a valuable repository for learning. Customisation and adaptation of these resources to suit institutional and regional contexts enhance their relevance and effectiveness.

Addressing the tools and infrastructure aspect, the establishment of an open-source initiative for AI tools in higher education is pivotal for affordability and accessibility. Furthermore, the implementation of European cloud infrastructures tailored for Large Learning Modules (LLMs) contributes to providing affordable access to essential resources, including infrastructure, data, computing capacity, and AI tools and technology.

Example of education programmes on AI in Sweden

One of the main challenges in education today is the exponential growth in knowledge and information that needs to be taught in a limited amount of time. There is therefore either a need to be selective with the content of the programmes, or a need to find ways of accelerating and enhancing the ways we teach and learn.

²³ <https://claire-ai.org/?lang=fr>

²⁴ <https://ki-campus.org/front>

The national Swedish context on the AI innovation and competence research ecosystem was introduced. It includes universities, and several research programmes and initiatives:

- The WASP²⁵ (Wallenberg AI Autonomous Systems and Software Program), with a budget of 600 million euros over 15 years and with a goal of educating at least 600 PhDs; in the area of AI autonomous systems and software, the programme currently has around 450 PhD students, and so far approximately 100 PhDs have been produced. It is a large-scale effort with a strong focus on education and competence development in this area; the WASP-ED programme is closely related to this program.
- WASP-HS²⁶ focuses on humanities and social sciences.
- The 'AI Competence for Sweden' initiative focuses on professional development within AI.
- AI Sweden²⁷ has the main goal of accelerating the use and applications of AI in Sweden.

These Swedish initiatives are also involved in a European ecosystem, such as TAILOR²⁸, a network of research excellence centres focused on providing scientific foundations for trustworthy AI in Europe, or TrustLLM²⁹ (Trustworthy and Factual LLMs made in Europe), an EU project on building trustworthy and factual large language models.

The WASP-ED programme's goal is to increase the capability and capacity of Swedish universities to provide timely, relevant, and scalable education in AI and other transformative technologies. It is a 3-year project, focused on the national perspective and trying to lead on activities that no individual universities can develop alone, with a focus on higher education and professional development. With the development of these transformative technologies, there is a rapid increase in demand for technical competence, which is also broadening to other subjects and professions. In the Swedish context, AI education has been present since the 1980s, however, the challenge is now to offer it in other educational programmes (e.g. medical sciences, economy, law, etc.), which is non-existent yet. The content of AI education is also changing. In that respect, three particular challenges are highlighted:

- to reach a commonly agreed subject matter content
- to introduce AI in education beyond only specialised education
- to increase teaching capacity

The programme has 4 objectives:

- to provide the educational foundations for AI and related transformative technologies

²⁵ <https://wasp-ed.org/>

²⁶ <https://wasp-hs.org/>

²⁷ <https://www.ai.se/en>

²⁸ <https://tailor-network.eu/>

²⁹ <https://trustllm.eu/>

- to scale-up the national educational capacity in AI and transformative technologies including educating and maturing the teaching staff to make use of and be innovative in the application of AI and transformative technologies in education
- to scale-out education in AI and transformative technologies to disciplines and professions beyond the technical core
- to develop data-driven education and pedagogical transformation using learning analytics

The programme is divided into six working groups (Curriculum, Program, Course, Pedagogy, Platform, Competence), so that progress can be made at all levels. Examples of actions include dialogues with universities on how to introduce AI in all university programmes or developing short courses for teaching staff to be able to teach AI from their own disciplinary perspective.

In the WASP-ED AI Curriculum (Lindgren & Heintz, 2023), the technical core remains, relating to core AI functionality, but the curriculum was broadened to become more socially and individually embedded (e.g. human-AI collaboration) and to include societal perspectives (e.g. ethical, legal, social, economical, cultural aspects, trustworthy AI). They also address socially and physically constrained infrastructures (Distributed and Edge AI, Robotics, Control and Autonomy Systems), applied AI in research and society, the history and futures of AI and fundamentals of knowledge. Events and seminars are regularly organised, thus building a community around the programme.

In answering the main question posed for this workshop, the following points were brought up:

1. So far there have been efforts put into strengthening digital competence, but computational thinking should be developed, i.e. teaching how to solve problems using computers as part of the process (Heintz, 2022). Computational thinking and AI are very connected, but AI is about getting computers to be better at problem-solving by learning, while computational thinking is how people become better at problem-solving by using computers.
2. To scale out and up the AI teaching, courses can be automated, such as in Elements of AI³⁰. For example, the University of Helsinki in Finland proposes an online course, with the goal of educating 1% of the Finnish population, which was achieved in 1 year and then broadened to the world. Sweden was the first case study. The courses can be started and completed at any time, as well as examinations, which challenges the concept of university. Around 1000 student are examined every semester, all this with the support of 1 part-time position (Heintz & Roos, 2021).
3. AI literacy (MacGrath et al, 2023; K.; Sperling et al, 2023; Katarina Sperling et al, 2023; Stenliden & Sperling, in press; WASP-HS, 2023) and competence development (Dell'Acqua et al, 2023; Dignum, 2019; Long & Magerko, 2020) are a priority area (Vuorikari Rina et al, 2022), and there are lessons to be learned already now from the Swedish AI Competence programme (Heintz et al, 2021).³¹

How do universities become better at providing professional education?

³⁰ <https://www.elementsofai.com/>

³¹ <https://ai-competence.se/>

- Universities operate on the long term, but it becomes very challenging for them to change things, and to change quickly, i.e. adapting programmes and teachers from one year to the next.
- Competence development in AI has to spread to all education programmes at all levels, starting with primary education, with a focus on how AI technology influences subjects. The focus should not be on the technology itself, but more on how the technology influences and changes the subjects.
- Current scientists can be trained through programmes such as the Swedish AI Competence initiative, but it is key to train the next generation with appropriate knowledge, which is not the case yet.

Empowering all users to use AI effectively

Currently, to get insights and answers using AI, scientists need an AI expert to build an AI model, which is a lengthy process. There is also a lot of reliance on AI experts to interpret the output of AI models. In the future, scientists could be directly empowered to build and interact with the AI systems and get the insights and answers much more directly, although AI experts will still be needed for foundational research in AI. To reach this more direct interaction, there is a need for AI literacy and skills, transparency and explanations, auditing, and development.

Figure 1

Main obstacles to empowered interactions between users and AI systems in science

Transparency

Understanding how AI models work and how they come to present certain outputs is critical for knowledge creation and in high-risk/high-harm applications. Understanding is also crucial for trustworthiness, to create trust and reliance on the knowledge that is created and how it is applied. Finally, understanding facilitates auditing and development (see Figure 1).

Explainable AI was based on the DARPA³² Program in 2016 which has been the impetus for an explosion in explainable AI research. David Gunning (Gunning et al, 2019) also proposed we move towards an explainable or transparent AI system where explanations are provided to the user, which then provide the basis for them to understand why certain decisions were made. This ensures the user has a calibrated or appropriate trust in an AI system (Adebayo et al, 2018; Kim et al, 2018; Ribeiro et al, 2016; Varshney, 2019). This work was carried out on machine learning but also more recently on deep learning. Work has also been carried out from a human perspective, i.e. on intelligibility and what kind of issues need to be explained, or what are good presentation formats for providing explanations. Work has also been done on the effects of explanations (Kulesza et al, 2015; Lim & Dey, 2010; Stumpf et al, 2009; Szymanski et al, 2021), their effects on understanding, on mental models, on trust, etc.

There are several challenges for explainable AI in science:

- Transparency and understanding are rarely evaluated with scientists who do not have an AI background (Bove et al, 2023; Caruana et al, 2015; Gunning et al, 2019; Miller, 2019). When engaging with explainability, one needs to take into account the target audience of the explanations, their expertise, their understanding, their background, and design them and implement them in an appropriate way.
- A lot of work focuses on increasing trust in AI (Buçinca et al, 2021; Bussone et al, 2015; Chromik et al, 2021; Eiband et al, 2019; Holliday et al, 2016; Lakkaraju & Bastani, 2019; Nourani et al, 2019) instead of calibrating trust, answering the question: 'how *much* can I trust the outputs of an AI system?'. Work is also starting now on how we can calibrate trust, how we can measure trust and how this differs from reliance.
- Explanations, when provided, are essentially handcrafted at the moment, they tend to be very specific to the use case on a specific application (Wang et al, 2019), there is currently an absence of guidelines on how to craft or design explanations for generic situations and users. There is no evidence base here that can be used to develop design patterns.

Auditing

Auditing consists in tools that are necessary to be able to identify 'bugs', for example if the AI model has learned something that is false or wrong, based on flawed data, or if the models have biases. This is critical in establishing trustworthiness and facilitates later development (see Figure 1).

There has been a lot of work carried out on fairness metrics and bias mitigation approaches (Bellamy et al, 2019; Mehrabi et al, 2019; Verma & Rubin, 2018). For example, the AI fairness 360³³ toolkit that was developed by IBM uses certain mechanisms to detect biases, and to identify and mitigate fairness issues. This is, however, mainly aimed at AI developers.

³² <https://www.darpa.mil/program/explainable-artificial-intelligence>

³³ <https://ai-fairness-360.org/>

Some challenges in auditing can be highlighted:

- End-user testing is in its infancy (Chen et al, 2022; Groce et al, 2014): involving the scientists in the testing is important, especially when defining and assessing bias and fairness criteria.
- Tools are needed that involve end-users in identifying bias and defining fairness for an AI model (Ahn & Lin, 2019; Cabrera et al, 2019; Nakao et al, 2022; Saha et al, 2020; Yan et al, 2020; Zhang et al, 2020). There are some positive steps towards this, more recently, such as FAIRVIS,³⁴ but auditing workbenches or tools workable by scientists do not exist yet.

Development

In the development phase, one would typically address and resolve the programming errors detected through the auditing tools. Development also underpins rapid knowledge creation and application.

There is currently not much work carried out on AI end user development or in enabling scientists to develop their own AI models. There is some work that has started to develop in human-in-the-loop learning, either in active learning or in Interactive Machine Learning approaches (Das et al, 2013; Kulesza et al, 2015; Lee et al, 2019; Mosqueira-Rey et al, 2023; Stumpf et al, 2009; Wang et al, 2022), but nothing that can be used as a workbench for scientists. There are also some interactive machine teaching approaches that people have started to look at.

But one challenge facing development are a lack of platforms that support AI development for scientists (e.g. <http://www.wekinator.org>). There is also a need for underpinning AI literacy and skills that are necessary for development (Ramos et al, 2020).

Conclusion

There is a need to empower scientists to use AI effectively. In order to do that, we need more focus on AI transparency, providing explanations, auditing and development tools in science, to speed up knowledge, creation, which is underpinned by AI literacy and skills.

With good explanations and increased transparency, the reliance on AI experts to provide the interpretation of the of the output could diminish. The auditing phase is also still very much in the hands of AI experts, for example through the use of fairness metrics. In the development phase as well, scientists rely on AI experts to choose, train and evaluate the models. Development platforms that allow scientists to create some of the models themselves would be a good way forward. Specialised AI skills will still be necessary for the access to higher performance computing.

³⁴ <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8986948>

Research careers in the context of digitalisation

There is still very little data available to assess the impact of AI on doctoral education and research careers. The technological landscape is also changing very rapidly, so predicting the future is challenging.

Current challenges in research careers

In order to implement AI in research careers appropriately, there is first a need to consider the present challenges in research careers. There is currently a high level of perceived mental well-being problems in research professions, with 32 to 42% of academic employees at risk of developing common psychiatric disorders (Levecque et al, 2017), with still very low awareness of these issues (Guthrie et al, 2017; Kismihók et al, 2019; Mattijssen et al, 2020)³⁵. These issues stem partly from working conditions, which include issues, like uncertain career prospects (Kismihók, 2021), precarious jobs, or the publish-or-perish culture. Awareness (personal, institutional or national) is still limited. Internal conflicts, work-life balance and financial problems in some regions further compound the challenges (Kismihók, 2021).

Against this backdrop, a Declaration on Sustainable Researcher Careers was published in 2019 (Kismihók et al, 2019), calling on research institutions, funding bodies and governments to ensure sustainable researcher careers. The Researcher Mental Health Manifesto (2021)³⁶, and the associated paper of (Kismihók et al, 2022) also contains evidence of these issues. There is therefore a need to seriously consider these challenges while developing the uptake of AI in the scientific world and research processes. This is important, as AI tools influence the research process, from ideation to publication, and researchers need to adapt to this new work environment to remain competitive, which adaptation may be difficult due to the listed concerns above.

Opportunities

A major advantage of the introduction of AI tools is their ability to provide a personalised support for research work and researcher training. AI tools can be adjusted to the personal research needs, considering unique, individual goals, experiences, and research contexts. AI tools can be seen as personal assistants, performing some tasks (like administration) quicker and in a more efficient way, while researchers' time can be invested more in their core tasks. The question of personalised use to reduce added pressure on early career researchers may be debatable. The alleviation of work on the one hand can lead to higher workload on the other, e.g. in the task of marking examinations, where staff members now need to find ways of detecting the use of AI, or how to evaluate it. The broad picture seems much more complex.

³⁵ <https://www.cactusglobal.com/mental-health-survey/>

³⁶ <https://zenodo.org/records/5788557>

Training

Access to AI technology is therefore key, but there exist major inequalities in access across regions and sectors³⁷ (Mihai et al, 2023). Consequently, training becomes imperative. The European Commission's digital targets for 2030³⁸ aim for example at training 20 million ICT specialists by 2030, or at achieving basic digital skills across at least 80% of the European population. The workplace increasingly demands AI skills, especially for high-skills jobs (OECD, 2023) but it is currently unclear if some jobs will disappear or on the contrary will be boosted if the AI tool can be used by the employees.

Training is needed to develop, use and reflect on AI (OECD, 2023), focusing not only on technical skills, but also on skills to adopt, use and interact with AI applications. However, this does pose a challenge if researchers need to get technical, transversal and domain-specific skills at the same time.

Despite these challenges, there is a wealth of openly available content and educational frameworks for AI training, such as The Digital Competence Framework for Citizens.³⁹ Based on an analysis of 11365 Coursera descriptions, it is estimated that 369 courses on AI are already available, which is encouraging, with many bottom-up projects in the field, such as OSCAR (Online, Open Learning recommendations and mentoring towards Sustainable research CAREers)⁴⁰ or eDoer,⁴¹ an open community-based AI-driven learning platform. There are hackathon formats that help researchers for preparing to this new working environment, such as Eduverse.⁴² And finally on research data literacy one can mention the Data Literacy Alliance.⁴³ There are also initiatives such as the European Skills, Competences and Occupations (ESCO),⁴⁴ which shows the emergence of AI in occupations and skills across the EU.

In conclusion, we need to be aware of the current problems with research careers when addressing AI in the academic workplace. It is essential to stay open, transparent, and brave in experimenting with AI applications, while remaining mindful of upcoming European AI legislation.

Hybrid intelligence: deskilling, upskilling and reskilling scientists

Elon Musk stated that AI will create a future where no job is needed and that 'the AI will be able to do everything'⁴⁵. However, other perspectives should be envisaged (Rafner et al, 2023). These tools offer an

³⁷ <https://www.pwc.com/gx/en/issues/analytics/assets/pwc-ai-analysis-sizing-the-prize-report.pdf>

³⁸ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/europe-fit-digital-age/europes-digital-decade-digital-targets-2030_de

³⁹ https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/digcomp/digcomp-framework_en

⁴⁰ <https://projects.tib.eu/oscar-ai/about-the-project/>

⁴¹ <https://www.edoer.eu/>

⁴² <https://oediverse.eu/>

⁴³ <https://dalia.education/>

⁴⁴ <https://esco.ec.europa.eu/en>

⁴⁵ <https://fortune.com/2023/11/03/elon-musk-ai-no-job-needed-work/>

immense innovative potential if in the hands of creative, business or scientific domain expert. A key focus now is how to get these tools in the hands of experts at an early stage, so they can demonstrate what type of interface or technology they need without depending on AI researchers and software developers.

Furthermore, AI most often can be applied only in specific parts of a job and cannot replace a job as a whole. For example, radiologists do far more than simply interpreting the outcome of a diagnostic image. It is important not to confuse a particular element of someone's job with the job in its entirety.

Hybrid intelligence

Hybrid intelligence has become a very common concept now. Nearly all AI today is considered as "in the loop", where human is involved in the process. But two strands of approaches emerge from there. On the one hand, some research is moving towards an 'on the loop' approach, with human only at the verification stages, and finally also 'out of the loop' with a complete autonomous operation. In this approach, the disruptive potential seems high, with a risk of bias amplification, deskilling, perverse instantiation, and value alignment 'flash crashes' in complex systems (high frequency trading, automated news reports, hacking IoT⁴⁶). On the other hand, we see the existence of a "computer in the loop" approach, used mostly in the human-centred AI community and human computer interactions⁴⁷ community, where AI is seen as a tool for human augmentation. Some experts call for pursuing simultaneously high degrees of automation *and* human control (Shneiderman, 2020), however, by considering AI only as a tool there is a risk of missing on the benefits of the AI disruptions, e.g. improving workflows. That is why there is a call for the development of hybrid intelligence, which is in many ways quite similar to human-centred AI but does not limit AI as a tool and moves the focus to mutual learning.

With such an approach, where humans and AI are considered as integrated, workflows in the real world (in companies or in the research workflow) can be addressed differently and the technology can be adapted. To reap the benefits of AI tools and especially generative AI, the non-AI experts need to be considered as AI-innovators and the challenge is to get them to become innovators. That cannot be done by merging AI and human-centred AI only, but by bringing in all the fields of research (Rafner, Bantle, et al, 2022) and by moving towards an interdisciplinary framework of hybrid intelligence, involved from development to deployment. For example, in the management sector, this would entail the implementation of a pact between leadership and employees, stating that a goal of transformation is not necessarily optimisation of processes, but rather the upskilling of employees. This creates a psychological safe space, which opens up opportunities for creating integrated solutions. Hybrid intelligence is therefore not only an interface, but also a structure that allows to focus on upskilling and empowerment, and on the rethinking of the entire value generation stream. There could therefore be great value in understanding more deeply the human role in all aspects of a job-cycle, at the risks of deskilling and the potential for upskilling (Elrod & Tippett, 2002; Rafner et al, 2021). There is great potential in thinking about integrating AI into the organisational context, so that end users also become co-creators and co-developers (Sherson et al, 2023).

⁴⁶ Internet of Things

⁴⁷ Human-computer interaction

Aarhus University has developed workshops for organisations. These workshops allow to experience and explore the potential of AI in their workflows, its impacts and potential to reshape the workflow patterns. To accept the technology, a crucial aspect is that end users need to be engaged in the design process. This calls for better understanding of what determines their buying into designing and training these tools (Mao et al, 2023). Applied to the field of science, these workshops propose research challenges in the form of games, to understand the flow between intuitive and computational interactions. The people who helped the most to develop these interfaces were the researchers themselves, because it allowed them to think differently about their complex tasks, and to present and pose them in completely new ways⁴⁸. This can be investigated in the domain of citizen science (Rafner, Gajdacz, et al, 2022). Another experiment also showed that, in a game, AlphaZero combined with detailed methodologies of quantum researchers *in* a hybrid approach was the most efficient (Dalgaard et al, 2020). So, these hybrid interfaces should be investigated much more systematically.

Scientists are now studying the state-of-the-art in human-AI systems in quantum research and the potential for applying hybrid intelligence along each step of the research cycle and looking into generating clear and actionable recommendations allowing researchers in the field to apply the techniques and ideas of hybrid intelligence to their systems ('5 ways you can make your research hybrid intelligent', (Kukina et al, in preparation)).

Co-creativity

There remains a challenge of understanding human-AI co-creativity. Creativity is essential in a researcher's career, but currently research in the area of human computer interactions and AI is lacking insights from psychological sciences, so there is a need to develop a theory of human-AI co-creativity (Rafner et al, 2023) that is strongly informed both by psychological sciences as well as by human-AI interaction. This ranges from trying to better understand co-creativity through human dyadic and team creativity, looking at benefits such as a physical, mental health and wellbeing, and how do these elements transfer to this interaction that has become prevalent in many different areas, using generative AI. This could shed light on how generative AI can help us enhance a product complexity of items, to gain a better understanding of creative abilities on a shorter time span.

This can raise concerns about the increasing risk of dehumanising human tasks and increasingly pushing humans to work in a machine-like way, but key in this approach is to use human skills to rethink processes and workflows. To mitigate the risk of depending on AI experts to facilitate these processes, the focus should be on empowering researchers to use it, so that AI researchers are not the impetus for innovation.

⁴⁸ <https://scienceathome.org/>

Epistemology of AI in science and impact on people

Discovery and verification

Hans Reichenbach (Reichenbach, 1938) put forward the difference between “context of discovery” and “context of justification”, proposing that the generation of knowledge is an individual psychological process, but once a knowledge claim has been made the scientific community takes on the role to justify it, i.e. to verify it and test it. This theory⁴⁹ allowed us to have a deeper understanding of what counts as scientific, by detaching the context of discovery from the context of verification. In the context of discovery, following a scientific method is not key in generating new knowledge (strict empiricism is not necessary), and this accepts intuition, unmethodological experiments, guesswork and luck, and even metaphysics as valid knowledge-generating approaches. In the context of verification, however, the method of verification is based on strict empiricism, it must have internal logical consistency, go through falsification attempts (as put forward by Karl Popper) and results must be reproducible.

This distinction becomes useful to consider the role of AI in science. The AI tool can produce useful ideas, insights and even hypotheses, and can be valued the same way as any other means of knowledge generation. The fact that it was not generated by a human or that the AI is a black box belongs to the context of discovery, therefore it does not matter. The reason for that is that tying methodology and outcomes, i.e. considering that the value of your knowledge is as good as your methodology, has failed on a logical level as well as in the history of science, so knowledge generated by AI must be accepted in the same way as knowledge generated by a human being. But this also implies that this knowledge needs to be verified.

Rewarding the work of justification

So an important proposed step forward is to start rewarding or at least acknowledging the work of justification (i.e. reviews, debate sessions) at least as much as knowledge creation and synthesis. This work has now become more important than ever, and policy can play a very important role in changing the norms associated with the context of verification. A success story of the EU was the propagation of Open Access by funding rules and other means. A similar approach is advised to promote review and reproduction of the scientific outcomes, at least on a similar level as the generation of knowledge claims. This truly demands a change in the norm that original claims enjoy higher perceived status than reproducing, double-checking others. But this norm has to be changed.

⁴⁹ Other experts have noted that this theory (distinguishing between discovery and justification) is contested in contemporary philosophy of science, with the argument that the ways in which science is verified strongly affect how discovery processes take place, and vice versa.

The reason for that is that with the help of AI, writing and publication will become easier, so more and more original ideas, theories and texts can be created. As the scarcity of these disappears, so the value must drop, as the rules of the market dictate – even the market of thoughts.

One approach to counter that is ensuring a level of scarcity. For example, is the publication (and peer review) of over 100 publications per year per author acceptable? Surely not, as it would mean two publications per week. Still this phenomenon can sometimes be observed. Obviously, no one ever should be prevented from publishing this often, but in a candidate evaluation process it could be prescribed that only 10,20 relevant publications can be taken into account and never a total sum. Therefore, quality over quantity will prevail as the authors are no longer incentivised to generate more publications, rather they will try to always replace a weakest link in their limited portfolio.

Another argument for such a limitation is the amount of review work that needs to be carried out to cater for such a frequent author. Is this work appropriately measured and rewarded? We argue it is not, therefore the quantitative expansion created by ill-designed scientometrics creates negative externalities by taking up the energy of those who can still be made to review. Some schemes already exist to quantify and reward the “justification” work, such as ORCID review acknowledgements or Publons,⁵⁰ or submitting articles to platforms that propose open peer review (e.g. Qeios).⁵¹

Some measures that could be put in place to counter the proliferation of poorer quality papers could be the implementation of quotas on number of publications that can be taken into account by any committee (remember: ideally these are also read!) as explained above. Another approach is a prescribed ratio to balance reviewer work and publishing work (i.e. at least twice as many verified reviews as publications). However, this could be controversial as scientists might have different strengths and such a system might hinder them too – still, the emergence of AI might leave no other choice.

There is therefore a need to balance discovery and justification. Besides a prescribed balance between discovery (generating knowledge, ideas, theses, articles) and justification (verification, reproduction, falsification, discussion), there are cultural elements, too. It is in Europe’s best interest to establish the ideal of a non-Stachanovistic European Scientist who prioritises quality over quantity in research and does not compete in quantity with the rest of the world. Some scholars suggest that many of the challenges mentioned are being addressed by the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (COARA).⁵² This coalition calls on the European Commission to be active in reforming the way research assessment is carried out, and the impacts of AI could be addressed as part of this initiative. While COARA is a good start, as it emphasises quality and recognizes the work in the context of justification, it can only be seen as a first step as it does not offer specific norms.

⁵⁰ Publons was a commercial website that provided a free service for academics to track, verify, and showcase their peer review and editorial contributions for academic journals. It was launched in 2012 and was bought by Clarivate in 2017.

⁵¹ <https://www.qeios.com/>

⁵² <https://coara.eu/>

Impact of AI on people in science

Regarding the impact of AI on people in science, one can look at it borrowing the conceptual toolkit of disruptive innovation⁵³. In this approach, the incumbent is disrupted by an entrant into the market. The entrant quickly fills an overlooked need, serves an underserved segment in the market, then it takes over as the incumbent has no time or awareness to react. There is a risk that such a phenomenon applies to humans (as incumbents) and AI (as entrant) on the job market, the competitive space among students and researchers, and in a market of self-worth as well. A good example is translation: in the early years of google translate or similar services, these did not stand a chance against a human professional. Yet, on the fringes of this market AI was already useful: being in a pinch in a foreign country, in need of understanding a label on the bottle or interacting with a local, an AI app on a smartphone has been the best buy for a long time. As the quality was low, sometimes ridiculously so, the market of translations was not disrupted. However, as AI first approached then matched the quality of human translators, the market is disrupted forever. The fear is that this process will be replicated. In the context of universities, students are already using AI as it boosts their productivity in fulfilling curriculum requirements, which can leave more time for other activities such as having a job. But many risks come with this use, such as technological lock-in with the sole use of ChatGPT, unclear rules about its usage leading to unfair grading facing an unequal use of the tool, which can undermine the system eventually.

Adopting AI in various roles could be a way of fleeing forward. But here comes the next issue: AI user skills are unevenly distributed if left untouched. Finally, the motivation for intellectual work must be put on a better footing. Just like with physical labour, it could turn out that we cannot compete with machines in intellectual labour either. And yet, it is in our interest to maintain control, just like with our physically powerful machinery. We can observe that humans do physical activities, like sport regardless as the value in it is not derived from the kinetic work done, but from maintaining a self-image. Similarly, we will need a way to perform mental activities not because we are the only one that can do so, but because it is part of a self-image we want to maintain.

Some scholars strongly disagree with a framing that opposes human to machines, arguing that humans and machines together can actually do better work. However, this can be a question of perspective because the distribution of AI is very uneven, and the idea of reskilling and upskilling can probably only work in a minority of places, while in most other places jobs will probably be lost.

To conclude, in the age of AI science of justification of knowledge is key. In education, the motivation of intellectual work is key, and there it is important to avoid platform lock-in. There is some agreement that the research system has now to change due to this powerful technology, and important measures should come from the top, like requirement for gender equity plan, the requirement for open access.

⁵³ <https://hbr.org/2015/12/what-is-disruptive-innovation>

Changing research environments in the context of AI and open science

Current issues in research environments

The self-referential and hyper-competitive research publishing system leads to an emphasis on volume and prestige over quality and reproducibility; the dominance of STEM subjects as the primary model for research leads to neglecting other approaches in arts and humanities; non-academic perspectives and knowledges are often undervalued despite their increasingly recognised importance, creating disparities in resource access. But many concerns are raised outside the publishing system as well: data, models and methods are considered more as secondary outputs in the research processes; there exists a high reliance on digital and physical infrastructure with too little consideration about their sustainability; and c) keeping track of research carried out with industrial and military funding is challenging. This contributes to a lack of insight into the broader research landscape.

Discrimination, racism, and colonial history cast a long shadow over scientific practices and the development of AI. This creates divides within research and hinders the relationship between research environments and society, especially concerning public interest and the diversity of publics involved in research or researched. Acknowledging these issues doesn't easily translate into actionable solutions, particularly in the context of AI development. This difficulty contributes to the strained relationship between research and society, with uncertainty being weaponised and open resources used to manipulate interpretations, as seen in debates around climate change. There is a strong push to regard scientific research as an ultimate source of truth, which clashes with the dynamic and self-correcting nature of science. This tension has been evident during the pandemic, contributing to confusion and eroding public trust in scientific results.

One can also highlight the lack of incentives and rewards for responsible dissemination and scrutiny of research components, transdisciplinary collaboration and community participation, two-way dialogue with policy and addressing injustice and resisting discrimination, prejudice and racism.

Can AI help address these issues?

Open science and AI have been hailed as a solution to try and address some of these issues, to help facilitate a fast, efficient and free sharing of research outputs. It could help to manage Big Data and the digital transformation of research processes, to build on existing collections as public goods and data sharing norms/technology, to involve diverse publics and forms of scrutiny in science, thereby improving quality and addressing inequity and injustice, and to ensure the production of robust, reliable and socially responsive science and technology (European Commission et al, 2020).

There are several assumptions about AI-fuelled open science. These assumptions are about:

- the unlimited access: making any research element available at any time for everyone
- the digital transformation: it is a novel phenomenon, dependent on ICTs and enhanced by AI
- it is always good: it automatically improves the content of science as well as researchers' working conditions
- it is global: it can reach everybody with an interest in research, no matter where they are based
- equity in research production and consumption: it makes previously inaccessible resources available to those who may wish to use them and reduces workload by automating research and reporting tasks

Every one of these assumptions is problematic. Some research was carried out over the past 15 to 20 years specifically looking at a variety of manifestations of openness and open science across different research environments and different locations across the globe (see project PHIL_OS).⁵⁴ Through this project, a series of challenges were identified on the ground:

- There are very few incentives for researchers to think about the sustainable development or responsible use of (digital) technology. There is a stronger emphasis on novelty and 'cutting-edge' research, with a tendency for technodeterminism (problems can be solved through technological solutions), and too little emphasis is placed on training researchers to think through systemic implications of adopting new technologies.
- There are serious concerns with the commercialisation and privatisation of algorithms and related software, which can make them unaffordable, gives little control over intellectual property rights and the development or customisation of these.
- There is a lot of algorithmic bias, building on already biased research system, with a big digital divide in data availability, access and re-use, accompanied by a labour divide between those who can and those who cannot adapt their skills.
- There is an expanding gap between entrenched, visible, popular research endorsed by rich sponsors and marginalised, invisible, unpopular research which however is crucial to addressing global challenges. Technologies continues to be used as proxy for the quality control of data, they amplify already popular research lines, and exacerbate lack of confidence by low-resourced researchers or with those with lower skills.

An alternative vision of AI-fuelled Open Science should therefore include:

- a focus on responsible use, rather than focusing only on providing access, by supporting the critical and constructive scrutiny of what is being made available at a global level, and how it may be used
- examining and making explicit the value-judgements that are made when setting open research infrastructures and related AI, because these systems are intrinsically discriminatory

⁵⁴ <https://opensciencestudies.eu/>

- establishing transparent criteria for assessing which users are privileged in the access of certain platforms, which can be important to fuel trustworthiness of AI systems
- facilitating equity in research production and consumption: it makes previously inaccessible resources more easily available to those who may wish to use them for specific purposes (whose social and scientific value has been explicitly evaluated)

It is therefore proposed to reframe Open Science and its implementation by thinking first about what inclusive open science and AI systems may look like, to then engender a higher quality of research and transparency, rather than focusing on making the system more transparent (European et al, 2018) and expecting that this will announce the quality of the research and therefore the inclusivity of research processes (Leonelli, 2023).

Against this backdrop, some practical implications are proposed in three different areas. In research design and training:

- retain ground truth by training AI developers and domain-specific researchers to curate high-quality training data and monitor the use of 'bad' data (Beaulieu & Leonelli, 2022)
- develop skills and infrastructure for the long-term
- avoid techno-determinist utopia, putting a lot of emphasis on ethics and governance training and dedicated expertise in this area (e.g. Ethical Data Initiative to coordinate global efforts)⁵⁵

In research conduct:

- recognise the importance of human calibration and decision-making for the adequate running of algorithms: a suggestion is to move away from automating science as an end goal
- boost skills for interdisciplinary collaboration as a key organisational and training challenge, beyond the key expertise needed in computing, data science, ethics and governance, and domain-specific knowledge
- emphasise mixed methods as key skill: intertwining automated analysis, hands-on experimentation, observational and participatory studies
- put more emphasis on humanities, arts and social sciences subjects as models of best practice when it comes to the use of mixed methods

In management and evaluation:

- expand types of outputs, relevant interlocutors, and timing of publication and feedback
- support researchers' transition to Open Science: cannot be delegated down to researchers only
- value domain-specific expert knowledge as foundational for AI/OS deployment

⁵⁵ <https://ethicaldatainitiative.org/>

There exists a tension between the need for longer-term thinking and the policy timeframes, which can partly be addressed through the emphasis on the resources and skills needed for the maintenance and update of these systems.

Discussion and conclusions

There are differing views around the theme of upskilling, since AI is evolving very fast, it is difficult to predict in what areas the training should be prioritised. However, prompt engineering and the ability to be talking with computers and controlling generative AI is completely new and there seems to be an obvious need to upskill everyone very specifically on this, with a view of co-creating with the machine. Furthermore, the needs for upskilling are different depending on the research areas, e.g. natural sciences, social sciences, because AI opens new possibilities that are linked to the field and the methods usually employed.

There is an agreement on the fact that ethics and governance of these systems is not taken into account sufficiently yet, and on the fact that real interdisciplinarity also needs to be boosted in order to realise AI applications which are responsible, with public interest at heart. Interdisciplinary training programmes could achieve that, such as a doctoral programme at Exeter University on Environmental Intelligence.⁵⁶ These programmes create generations of researchers that have the necessary combination of skills, which can help break the existing disciplinary silos.

On skills, it can also be highlighted that computational thinking skills or AI thinking skills are needed, but also skills that relate to data collection and use in AI, which then leads to knowledge and skills on the ethical treatment and responsible treatment of the data and the models. All these aspects need to be combined. This will enable end users to work more closely with the machines rather than through an intermediary, and for that appropriate explanations need to be embedded in the AI tools, to create trust.

Some scholars are of the opinion that when it comes to training, the landscape is moving so fast that very quickly some classes could become obsolete or counterproductive. However, raising awareness about the use of these tools and providing a framework for their use is key.

On geographical disparities, AI access also needs good internet and electricity, these are important prerequisites that are not present equally across Europe. There exist technical solutions to these issues, informed by a qualitative understanding of the situation. There are a few initiatives around low bound technologies, developing algorithms that are specifically suited to environments which have very little infrastructure. Even more critical to even disparity in AI use is IP protection. Very often participants from marginalised backgrounds provide inputs into these systems, which are then being used in ways that may harm them, without having any say in the process. Regulatory work looking at questions intellectual property and benefit-harm analysis would be very important here, to create trust in these systems. However, some scholars see AI as an opportunity to reduce these infrastructure inequalities, and AI access inequalities.

⁵⁶ <https://www.exeter.ac.uk/study/pg-research/degrees/climatechange/environmental-intelligence/>

Workshop report

Because now these tools are accessible by typing some text, in a way that was not possible only recently. This represents an immense potential for more marginalised communities or low-tech environments.

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Workshop participants

Expert participants

- **Patrícia Martinková**, Czech Academy of Sciences (workshop chair and moderator)
- **Stephane Berghmans**, European University Association
- **Anna Fabijańska**, Lodz University of Technology
- **Mihály Héder**, Budapest University of Technology and Economics
- **Fredrik Heintz**, Linköping University
- **Gábor Kismihók**, TIB - Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology
- **Tomáš Kozubek**, Technical University of Ostrava
- **Sabina Leonelli**, University of Exeter
- **Arlindo Oliveira**, Instituto Superior Técnico
- **Janet Rafner**, Aarhus University
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- **Ute Schmid**, University of Bamberg
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- **Helen Eenmaa**, President of YASAS, Member of the SAPEA Board
- **Marie Franquin**, Scientific Policy Officer
- **Stephany Mazon**, Scientific Policy Officer
- **Céline Tschirhart**, Scientific Policy Officer
- **Alaa Jbour**, Communications Manager
- **Rudolf Hielscher**, Coordinator

Workshop methods

Expert selection

In the context of the request for Advice on the topic ‘Successful and timely uptake of Artificial Intelligence in science in the EU’ SAPEA issued a call for nominations on 18 July 2023, describing the scope, timeline and expertise required. The call for nominations was sent via the academy networks to their member academies, who were invited to nominate experts following the procedure described in the SAPEA Quality Assurance Guidelines⁵⁷. Experts involved in the workshop were selected from the list of nominees. Additional experts were also identified through desk research by the academy networks. The list of areas of expertise that should be covered in the workshop was established in coordination with the SAM Secretariat and the member of the SAPEA working group in charge of key area 3.

The experts were selected by SAPEA and the member of the working group in charge of key area 3 on the basis of scientific excellence and disciplinary requirements as a priority, taking into account commitment and time availability, and the criteria set out in our strategy of diversity and inclusiveness:

- inter- and multidisciplinary
- involvement in the wider scientific community;
- inclusion of early- and mid-career researchers
- gender balance
- wide geographical coverage, including from Widening countries

The final group of experts who attended the workshop included 47% of female experts. 7% of attending experts were early-career and 53% mid-career researchers. 33% of experts came from Widening Countries. The following countries were represented by the experts: Belgium, Czechia, Denmark, Germany, Hungary, Poland, Portugal, Sweden, United Kingdom, Switzerland.

Workshop process

Experts received the scoping paper along with the questions posed in key area 3 in advance of the workshop. They were asked to present on the scientific topic of interest, related to their area of expertise. In line with the SAPEA principle of transparency, workshop expert participants were asked to declare any conflict of interest and any interest that might be perceived by SAPEA as a conflict of interest in relation to this scientific topic at the beginning of their presentations.

⁵⁷ SAPEA, Science Advice for Policy by European Academies. (2023). Quality assurance guidelines and procedures on science advice for policy and society. Berlin: SAPEA. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8329539>

Experts also received specific instructions about the format of presentations:

- listing the scientific publications cited in the presentations
- preparing the content of the presentation by drawing on their own research but also on their broad knowledge of the field
- keeping the confidentiality of participants until the publication of the report

The report summarising the workshop was prepared by SAPEA and sent to all experts present for feedback before publication. To encourage openness and the sharing of information, the public summary report was prepared in an anonymous, non-attributed style.

Workshop programme

- 09:00: Welcome
- 09:05: Background to the request
- 09:10: Introductory remarks
- Infrastructure of AI:
 - 09:15: European AI infrastructure access and sharing
- Education and skills development in AI:
 - 09:35: How can the training of AI researchers and specialists be improved?
 - 09:55: Education about AI, example from Sweden
- Human-computer interaction for scientists: transparency, careers and jobs:
 - 10:15: Empowering all users to use intelligent systems effectively
 - 10:35: Research careers in the context of digitalisation
 - 10:55: Hybrid intelligence: deskilling, upskilling and reskilling scientists
- 11:15: Break
- Research environments:
 - 11:30: Epistemology of AI in science and impact on people
 - 11:50: Changing research environments in the context of AI and open science
- Discussion and conclusions:
 - 12:10: Roundtable discussion on the guiding questions
 - 12:30: General discussion
 - 12:55: Wrap-up and conclusions
 - 13:00: Next steps and closing

Scientific Advice Mechanism

to the European Commission

Successful and timely uptake of artificial intelligence in science in the EU

10 January 2024

Policy design workshop report

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Introduction

Evidence-gathering expert workshops are a vital part of SAPEA's rapid evidence review process. Together with the literature reviews, they constitute the main avenue for evidence-gathering from the wider scientific community.

This evidence-gathering workshop for the topic *Successful and timely uptake of Artificial Intelligence in science in the EU* addressed Key Area 3 of the scoping paper¹: policy design. It was held on 10 January 2024, as a hybrid meeting online and in Brussels. Participants included the invited experts, all members of the working group, SAPEA representatives, the Group of Chief Scientific Advisors and staff of the European Commission.

The workshop format was as follows:

- At the beginning of each workshop day, SAPEA and the Advisors provided an introduction to the Scientific Advice Mechanism, the topic and the background to the request.
- One working group member was in charge of moderating the talks and discussions for each day. The invited experts presented evidence about the impact of AI on education and careers of the scientists and researchers.
- Each talk was followed by questions and the day ended with a general discussion between all participants.

The content of each presentation, the opinions shared by the experts and the discussions are summarised below. The names of all participants can be found at the end of this report, along with the workshop programme.

The evidence presented and discussed will directly inform the SAPEA evidence review report on the same topic available on the website², and the Scientific Advice Mechanism's advice to the European Commission.

The Group of Chief Scientific Advisors provides independent scientific advice to the European Commission. The Advisors work closely with the SAPEA consortium, which conducts comprehensive reviews of the evidence.

The scoping paper for *Successful and timely uptake of AI in science in the EU* sets out the formal request for advice from the European College of Commissioners to the Group of Chief Scientific Advisors.

¹ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-07/Scoping_paper_AI.pdf

² <https://scientificadvice.eu/advice/artificial-intelligence-in-science/>

Introduction

The evidence review report by SAPEA synthesises the evidence, in response to the main question from the scoping paper:

How can the European Commission accelerate a responsible uptake of AI in science (including providing access to high quality AI, respecting European Values) in order to boost the EU's innovation and prosperity, strengthen the EU's position in science and ultimately contribute to solving Europe's societal challenges?

The workshop on Key Area 4: Policy Design aimed to gather evidence to answer the question set out in the scoping paper under this key area:

How can the European Commission accelerate a responsible uptake of AI in science (including providing access to high quality AI, respecting European Values) in order to boost the EU's innovation and prosperity, strengthen the EU's position in science and ultimately contribute to solving Europe's societal challenges?

Workshop report

Actors of the ‘scientific and research communities across the EU’ — research undertaken in ‘private’ labs

Scientific knowledge created by a collaboration between many players across multiple organisations drives innovation. The distinction between knowledge co-creation versus its monetisation is at the heart of the AI research and innovation debate where a few players hold disproportionate power.

The global innovation systems in AI include large, dominant companies — many refer to them as Big Tech — that have intellectual monopoly. If many researchers work on a big puzzle trying to put different pieces together, the big companies hold the power to assemble those pieces and define what the puzzle will be about in the first place. All the organisations that directly or indirectly produce pieces of such a puzzle for a Big Tech integrate their corporate innovation system. AI global innovation system today overlaps with the corporate innovation system of a few Big Tech, which explains why, although thousands of organisations contribute to producing AI (research and innovation), Big Tech disproportionately profit and control the field.

Typically, innovation comes from scientific research which gets distributed for use in society. The distribution process is curtailed by the Big Tech because these companies turn jointly produced research into black-box services, notably through the cloud, and disproportionately profit from them. The policy discussion should be centred around how AI research is done for developing new AI tools and how even if it is conducted by many, in the end a few companies channel outcomes into paid service pipelines.

Systemic gatekeeping in AI research

The most important AI conferences between 2018 and 2020 were overwhelmingly occupied by Big Tech. The highest frequency of co-authorships at the conferences between 2018 and 2020 included people from Microsoft, Alphabet (Google), Meta (Facebook), Amazon, and several Chinese tech companies. By directly participating in writing papers and co-creating knowledge with Microsoft and other Big Tech companies, AI research is unfortunately largely steered by the companies (Rikap, 2023d).

This disparity partly comes from double affiliations, where academic researchers also work for Big Tech (Figure 1). The main appropriation mechanism for the Big Tech in this instance is to drive innovation at high speed while maintaining secrecy (Rikap, 2023d). Typically, most discussions in Big Tech occur through non-disclosure agreements as discovered by interviewing 90 AI scientists, engineers, developers, and managers in the Tech companies. Besides these secretly kept results, the research that is made public is controlled and serves the profits of Big Tech disproportionately. Among all the AI scientists, Microsoft is the key connector between researchers in Western countries and China, which means that the global agenda is significantly

steered by Microsoft's priorities. While 90% of Microsoft publications have co-authors from most AI academic institutions and other firms, the patents are entirely owned by Microsoft, thereby gatekeeping the current knowledge and the future of AI research (Figure 2, Rikap, 2023a).

Figure 1

Dual Affiliations in AI Research

Scientists working at Big Tech come from academic institutions across the world. Google and Microsoft attract AI scientists from more than 30 different institutions.

Graphic: Sejal Davla, PhD

The expert's analysis based on datasets from 14 AI conference presentations between 2012 and 2020 shows that AI scientists working at public research institutes also work for tech companies. The graph shows the number of research institutes.

Figure 2

Patent monopoly: The graph shows the majority of Microsoft publications have co-authors from academia; however, 99% of patents generated using knowledge from academic researchers are exclusively owned by Microsoft. Image created using data from Rikap (2023a), source: Web of Science (2012–2021)

AI code

AI algorithms are implemented through codes in different programming languages. There are two major concerns with how Tech companies use AI code (Rikap & Lundvall, 2022). The first one concerns open-source codes where companies adopt open-source policies for defined projects, attracting free work from hundreds of developers. GitHub is a code repository where thousands of programmers upload their codes publicly for teaching, reproducibility, and publishing purposes. Among the three GitHub projects by Microsoft, Meta, and Alphabet, the majority of knowledge in the form of codes was contributed by people who did not work at those companies. As more developers contribute, Big Tech open source solutions become the industry standard. Then, these companies then can develop complementary services that they monetise or, even more profitable, they can create an ecosystem on top of the open-sourced solution. By controlling necessary complements or the recombination of diverse pieces that make the solution a product, Big Tech charges fees to those participating, like Google with Android and its app store. Here, open sourcing attracts developers, which take the economic and innovation risks and are then locked in. This is precisely what Meta is trying to do today with Llama, its Large Language Model (LLM) (Figure 3).

Figure 3

Code capture: Code contributions on GitHub projects show knowledge and code generated by non-employees. Image created using data from Rikap and Lundvall (2022).

Summing up, pieces of knowledge that are not the core of Big Tech intellectual monopolies can be put in open source and, because those pieces only become a business once paired or recombined with other pieces kept secret, they profit from free work and advance adoption of their solutions without risking their businesses (Rikap & Lundvall, 2020; Rikap & Lundvall, 2022).

The case of Llama is particularly interesting because, even if the model is open source, using it requires processing power, thus it is usually deployed as a cloud service of a Big Tech cloud. Meta and Microsoft have a strategic partnership for Llama operating on Microsoft's Cloud Azure. Although Llama is a non-paid service, there is a charge to run it paid for the processing power consumed. Hence, using Llama on the cloud is not free, it is just that the price is charged on the compute (Rikap, 2023d).

The other aspect concerns the investments in AI startups. While AI startups need funding and funders can come from any domain, Big Tech remains the main AI Startup funder in 2023 (Rikap, 2023c, 2023d). For example, Microsoft controls 49% of OpenAI, the ChatGPT4 creator. This arrangement is strategic for Microsoft in controlling the innovation ecosystem.

According to a researcher working at a French startup Mistral AI, Big Tech also provides processing power. By providing this crucial infrastructure and offering software as services, Tech companies not only control AI research but also AI as a tool for innovation. For example, Amazon, one of the biggest cloud service

providers, offers not only cloud credits to startups but also specific credits for research programs (Rikap, 2023e).

Using private cloud services (which includes infrastructure as a service, platforms as a service, software as a service and even data as a service) further curtails learning and innovation because organisations, universities, and startups access pieces of code as black-boxed cloud services without gaining access to the code. Moreover, companies are consciously building their business models around reinforcing power relations between the Big Tech as providers of AI models offered as cloud services (sometimes even produced by third-party companies but still offered as services on Big Tech clouds) and the start-ups and other companies as users of AI. This further entrenches Big Tech power. With such business practices, it is inevitable that the more people uptake AI, the cloud demand will increase, thereby increasing the risk of dependence on big companies (Rikap, 2023b).

Key policy considerations

- Old solutions will backfire. Double affiliations are a serious problem, they transfer knowledge to Big Tech but nothing is gained by the public institution. Critically, AI uptake cannot be at the expense of more dependence on the US Big Tech. For people receiving European Commission funding, there must be policies in place to limit double affiliations.
- Bring Talent Back: Because Big Tech has a vested interest in increased AI uptake by the scientific community, simply increasing more horizon projects and more research and innovation policies will not work. By increasing AI research funding without caveats or conditionings, the predicted outcome will be feeding the Big Tech corporate machine through spending that money on private services, such as Cloud platforms and AI tools, and developing solutions that will end up running on Big Tech clouds, thus serving a fee to Big Tech each time those solutions are sold (just like in the app marketplaces). The public-private partnerships with these companies also will not work because they find mechanisms to appropriate these relationships that should otherwise be cooperative. Therefore, bringing the talent back from these companies to public institutions is the best way forward. Such endeavour requires changing the assessment and funding mechanisms within academia. AI researchers work for Big Tech because they provide all the resources without spending time writing grant applications.
- There needs to be sound governance policies to control who will have access to the results. This discussion needs to be more nuanced beyond just defining open source versus proprietary results because Big Tech also control the open source universe, more thoughtful property rights and licensing schemes could be put in place that favour truly public science while limiting private capture of publicly funded research. In addition, the teams that access results must be interdisciplinary, integrating people with expertise in ethics, social sciences, and technology.

Discussion highlights

Q: How to bring talent back to academia when Big Tech offers enormous incentives to the top AI scientists? Why researchers with better experience and easy access to powerful resources will come back to academia?

A: To address this question, the idea of talent needs to be defined. AI work requires skills in programming languages and coding. Bringing back talent means enticing people who do real work such as coding in the advancement of academic science. Top managerial position holders in the industry might lack the programming skills to develop new projects and they are not the target talent academia should aim for.

For example, many people at Google's DeepMind believed they would solve major challenges in AI. However, after witnessing ChatGPT4's success in the last year, DeepMind's workforce was steered towards developing products rather than focusing on research. A good strategy will be to identify people who want to come back to academia and discuss the alternative model to make them successful within the academic ecosystem. This alternative can be akin to the Oppenheimer project giving a lot of freedom, resources, and time to solve interdisciplinary problems without worrying about publishing their work in scientific journals, of course without the goal of building a weapon but solutions to major social and ecological challenges. From the interviews with researchers in Tech, they value contributing to research more than the salary, but they need to be able to work in an environment with 5 Ps: purpose, public datasets, processing power (the two latter are necessary, without them AI does not deliver), peers (AI requires a lot of people working together) and a relatively more competitive pay. People working in large interdisciplinary AI projects shall not be worrying about grants, resources, and publications, especially when the publications largely benefit Big Tech.

Q: How much infrastructure and resources do academics lack compared to private companies?

A: Massive! In the interview process a French AI scientist reported that when he left academia to work at DeepMind, he had access to more processing power as a single person on his first day of work than what was available to all French academics at that time.

What is 'responsible and timely' AI uptake in science in the EU?

Researchers in social science and humanities try to address what is responsible and timely AI uptake in science in the EU by interviewing interdisciplinary scientists who use AI and conducting critical reviews of current AI efforts. Their work reveals the impact of AI across five broad areas of research: design, conduct, dissemination, training, and research assessment. There are challenges and opportunities in each area that can inform sound policymaking.

Research design

With fast-growing AI capabilities in all research domains, different research tasks are affected to a degree (Leonelli, 2016a, 2017; Leonelli & Williamson, 2023). Many advocate delegating specific research tasks to automated systems, while some equate AI almost with automating research. Technologies like natural language processing (NLP) can serve this agenda; however, it is imperative to distinguish between what research tasks can be and should be automated.

Depending on the research field, there remains a lot of disagreement on automation. For example, tasks in genomics like microarray experiments that are constantly reinvented where the assay sensitivity and interpretation of results are context dependent. On the other hand, many experiments in biomedicine and clinical medicine, such as diagnostics assays generate predictable results with unambiguous interpretation. Therefore, it remains difficult to provide a standard for what constitutes a routine task that can be standardised through an AI application.

There should be a consensus in the research community about which routine tasks can be delegated to an automated system. Typically, automated systems get feedback based on how things were done in the past. To automate a task for future use, the process has to be standardised, yet the parameters used to carry it out may change in time (and sometimes very rapidly). For example, tasks that need constant reassessment on whether they will achieve the goals in the future might not be easily automated.

For any AI development, access to high-quality input data as the starting point is paramount (Leonelli, 2016b). However, there is relatively little investment and acknowledgement in creating infrastructures and skills to churn out high-quality data. The gap between creating proper training data and using them to train machine learning models is widening every minute. A counterargument to avoid making such an investment is that researchers can train the AI system to clean the input data. However, this strategy does not work in research where data cleaning and maintenance require contextualisation and interpretation based on domain-specific knowledge and case-by-case judgments (Leonelli, 2023). Another caveat of creating such a techno-determinist system where most tasks can be automated by AI is that it largely discredits ethics and governance considerations (Couldry & Mejias, 2019; von Borzyskowski et al, 2020).

While there is a consensus on AI adoption in research, the implications of automating research are largely unclear. The expectation is that automation will be cost-effective by reducing manpower and increasing research output. However, the savings may be offset by the requirements to buy and maintain expensive technology and to hire people with different/new skills to handle AI tasks (in an already saturated job market where such people require high salaries).

There must also be a distinction between doing science faster versus doing good science. For climate change and environmental emergencies (Leonelli, 2021), there are incentives to do science ever faster, however, it does not guarantee whether the results will be reliable and stand the test of time.

Research conduct

The calibration of AI systems and the decision-making process within these systems are critical aspects of research conduct to achieve reliable outputs. The research procedures and algorithms must be validated first before authenticating any outputs and findings produced by them. Even highly standardised procedures that are ideal for uptake by AI systems, need regular revision and updates of algorithms. Currently, there are no incentives to validate tasks that are delegated to AI systems. Moreover, relying on the AI system to update itself does not guarantee reliable outputs.

Domain-specific knowledge and people expertise are crucial for calibrating and updating AI systems (Leonelli, 2023). Additionally, combining interdisciplinary expertise in social sciences, ethics, and governance to generate quantitative and qualitative analyses offers a better understanding of AI system functions, behaviour, and applications (CCA, 2022).

Research dissemination

Knowledge dissemination through AI systems creates new kinds of challenges. With increased adoption of open science policies, AI systems can use publicly available information to create misinformation. It is already becoming difficult to distinguish between information versus misinformation for humans and AI systems. Because AI tools are opaque by definition (there is no underlying human reasoning to the outputs), it is often difficult to reconstruct the research process behind knowledge generation and dissemination. Moreover, the commercialization and privatisation of AI algorithms and software for research dissemination are also biased and opaque.

Research training

Training people in using AI tools effectively, adequately, and reliably is imperative to maintain research integrity. There is a gap in digital skills that continues to increase because researchers in low-resource environments without training facilities and infrastructure lack core competencies in how to use AI. There is also a perception bias where researchers in environments with low AI uptake tend to think their AI literacy is low, therefore, engaging less in AI work. Beyond the lack of training for AI skills, there is also a lack of training for sustainable AI development and its responsible use.

Research assessment

In research assessments, such as reviewing panels, promotion committees, and grant reviews, there are no experts who can evaluate AI research. Further, qualitative metrics for research assessment are reliable, but they are resource-intensive and can only be afforded by rich institutions and countries that can put a lot of manpower behind such evaluation. There are also efforts to automate the peer review process. However, they will remain problematic as long as the automated data quality checks are opaque (Milano et al, 2023).

Key policy considerations

- The focus must shift from delegating scientific tasks to AI to using AI intelligently to complement researchers in performing tasks. The ultimate goal should be not automating the research enterprise, including design, assessment, and training, but to perform standardised tasks more efficiently in less time.
- The research training should incorporate long-term goals and develop skills and infrastructures that work beyond 10–20 years.
- Retaining ground truth is very important, where the focus must be on curating high-quality training data with continued long-term investment in this effort. There should also be monitoring of how

bad data is used and identifying digital ecosystems that use unreliable data. There should be guidelines about improving such ecosystems through the removal of corrupted or erroneous data.

- Integrating ethics, governance, and critical data studies into AI training should be at the forefront of policymaking. There must be long-term systemic training programs that provide AI researchers with hands-on tools to confront new challenges, apply ethical frameworks to understand and solve them, and constantly evaluate them in terms of repercussions for society.
- The AI tools should be designed along with stakeholders, such as social scientists, reporters, and user groups from the beginning. Such effort requires long-term funding in venues that support social interactions around AI applications. There should also be a partnership with commercial providers that are yet to openly provide their frameworks on ethics and governance.

Discussion highlights

Q: How does AI science endanger transdisciplinary collaborations?

A: Interdisciplinary research includes computer scientists working with domain specialists, such as biologists, chemists, and physicists to devise solutions. When it comes to such transdisciplinarity work, researchers often complain about a lack of investment. For example, there is no institutional support for social scientists who want to understand the impact of a medical tool by engaging with patient groups or stakeholders outside of academia.

This disparity originates from speeding the research process with the sole focus on building a technological solution. For example, using AI to recognise patterns in certain cancers comes at the detriment of consulting with patients and families and their understanding of the technology through historical and social lenses. Further, the assessment of how such AI applications affect medical infrastructures and institutional policies requires transdisciplinary collaborations. Therefore, focusing on AI as a substitute for routine tasks can dampen important transdisciplinary collaborations that are fundamental to making the tasks robust and resilient for long-term use.

Geopolitics of AI: what implications for responsible science?

The concept of the geopolitics of AI is timely with the potential return of empires (Mialhe, 2018). With the mounting threat of the return of the empire, Europe lacks independence and strategic autonomy when it comes to AI. From an AI perspective, Europe is more or less an AI colony of the US and there needs to be a separation from that. While there is growing public investment from the EU, the capabilities and power of AI models remain cryptic.

The digital transformations in the last few years catalysed tremendous progress in AI as seen in the last two years. The majority of this progress converges between algorithms, compute infrastructure, and data that is predominantly built and led by Big Tech. Further, the prevailing infrastructure and business models guarantee disproportionate power in the hands of Big tech.

The scarcity of resources and the monopoly of Big Tech on AI research are other geopolitical challenges. AI research requires algorithms, data, and computing infrastructure. While algorithms circulate more easily than data and compute, it is the scarcity of resources that prevents researchers from doing cutting-edge research. For example, the microchips are the crushing monopoly of NVIDIA and Microsoft OpenAI's ChatGPT4 is crushing other large language models in its market uptake.³

Wars across the globe have returned with ongoing conflicts in Ukraine and Gaza and impending potential conflicts in Korea and the strait of Taiwan. AI is increasingly used to acquire and keep strategic dominance across several functions like intelligence, surveillance, and beyond. Starting from 2018 till now, there are growing strategic tensions and decoupling of the American and Chinese economies. The growing rivalry in AI between the two countries led to the US blocking AI access to China by imposing sanctions. These sanctions make it impossible to trade AI chips and computing infrastructure to Chinese AI developers.

These changes are happening much faster than anticipated resulting in growing challenges for academics to cooperate on cutting-edge AI research. For example, a Harvard Professor was sentenced and fined for lying about his ties with China by the US Department of Justice a few years ago. With this move, the US sent a clear message to academics and communities about new geopolitical boundaries.

Moreover, AI is increasingly considered a strategic asset. The emerging network of recently launched national AI safety institutes in the UK⁴ and USA, and potentially coming up soon in France, China, Japan, and India are examples of that. Each country is navigating between the boundaries of safety and security, particularly focusing on national security. For example, the UK Deputy National Security Advisor and the military have a seat on the AI institute's governing board because these institutes are tasked with understanding and evaluating dangerous capabilities with some directly related to national security. The national security considerations not only make it challenging to disseminate information, but they also include criminal liability, which is always enforced. Therefore, academics who cooperate on AI assets, knowledge pieces, and knowledge artefacts increasingly fall under the purview of national security.

Key policy considerations

- There needs to be a new form of scientific cooperation. The EU can engineer new modes of scientific cooperation resembling CERN's philosophy on the safe and responsible interpretability of AI models.
- The EU can build a network of national AI safety institutes by creating an EU AI Safety Institute, tasked with the same functions as its UK and US counterparts. These functions include developing and conducting evaluations of AI systems, driving foundational AI safety research, and facilitating information exchange among EU partners.

³ State of AI report 2023 <https://www.stateof.ai/> - slides 12 and 76

⁴ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/ai-safety-institute-overview/introducing-the-ai-safety-institute#contents>

- A ‘CERN-ish’ mechanism of cooperation can be at the centre of the computation. Taking lessons from the successes of the CERN model, a similar model can remove obstacles to scientific cooperation within national AI safety institutes.
- To advance the responsible uptake of AI in science in the EU, supporting all the labs doing AI research across the Union under a flagship project is required to galvanise new programs and research. For example, one such project emerged from the European Commission in the past years that developed a digital twin for the Earth⁵ for weather forecasting and climate action. While this project brings together different players for a common goal, it is deceptive in what it could deliver. Therefore, there must be a balance between what new flagship projects could offer and the risks they represent.

Discussion highlights

Q: What are the environmental implications of the geopolitics of AI?

A: They are still unknown, but they are estimated to be intense. However, it is difficult to predict what they could be. There are emerging tensions between prioritising the ecological transition and ensuring the sovereignty of Europe. For example, what if Google or Microsoft achieved carbon neutrality in their computing infrastructure more easily than a small player in Poland or France? With such a possibility, there needs to be a reconciliation on current geopolitical tensions and future regulatory capture.

How do AI and the open-source approach to AI in science affect the cybersecurity and security spaces?

AI and generative AI brought major concerns to the cybersecurity field. There is a long-standing history of using AI techniques for malware classification (Kapersky, 2021) and fraud detection (Bhatt et al, 2023; Frank et al, 2023). On the contrary, the same methods can be employed to harm systems in a myriad of ways affecting the cybersecurity space. For example, AI systems can morph viruses or support even novice users to write ransomware and malware⁶ or potentially lead to automatized attacks (Fang et al, 2024). Jailbreaking is another threat where AI models can expose devices to security risks by removing built-in safeguards. In the cybersecurity space, it is important to devise strategies on how to protect AI models against such malicious use (He & Vechev, 2023).

Additionally, intersectionality between software engineering and the use of AI in software engineering greatly impacts security. LLMs are already assisting software developers in code generation. The models also generate vulnerabilities or bugs in the coding process (Hajipour et al, 2023). Therefore, there needs to be thorough auditing mechanisms for the models and the codes generated with their help. Although it is yet

⁵ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/destination-earth>

⁶ <https://www.hyas.com/blog/blackmamba-using-ai-to-generate-polymorphic-malware>

difficult to assess how generating codes using LLMs is worse than coders using web search, the expectations from AI models must be to produce better code (Gupta et al, 2018; Gupta et al, 2017; Hajipour et al, 2019). Further, there should be new capabilities to fix and audit code at scale. In this regard, automated software testing along with authorised ethical hackers to assess code at scale would positively affect the security landscape.⁷

When it comes to cybersecurity, the emphasis must be on open-source practices, particularly on transparency and openness (Bommasani et al, 2023; Yu et al, 2020). For example, evidence suggests many of the jailbreak security and privacy leakage problems were identified by partially open models. Without the openness, the research community would not have had the capabilities to assess and test models for vulnerabilities, disclose these vulnerabilities to the community and industry – which in turn lead to an increase in security.

Certain cybersecurity issues, mainly fraud, impersonation, and deep fakes are exacerbated by AI (Mitchell et al, 2023; Sankar Sadasivan et al, 2023; Yu et al, 2018). For example, other than misinformation in all spheres, non-consensual pornographic deepfakes are a huge emerging problem.⁸

Co-pilot applications are another emerging security challenge as LLMs become application platforms. For example, Microsoft and OpenAI plugins are already integrated into Windows. Such business strategies violate some fundamental cybersecurity ideas where these models typically don't separate data and instructions and don't distinguish between trusted and untrusted inputs.

Key policy considerations

- The security researchers perform critical research against the strict rules of the companies, therefore, there should be protection and support mechanisms for them. There needs to be involvement from the security community to interact with, analyse, and vet AI products. This process should have solid disclosure guidelines including how the vulnerabilities are reported.
- With AI becoming part of the entire IT ecosystem, having cybersecurity standards for everyone can be a paradigm shift. These standards should allow vulnerabilities to be tracked in a reliable way and must improve transparency.
- Watermarking, a method for insinuating the owner of a digital object to determine the intellectual property process needs to be streamlined to determine what information is synthesised by AI (Abdelnabi & Fritz, 2020). While watermarking is not a sustainable solution in the long run, it can contribute to mitigation techniques, but needs to be continuously evaluated with care, so that the draw backs do not outweigh the benefits and no false sense of security is generated.

⁷ <https://uk.pcmag.com/security/146150/microsoft-uses-chatgpt-tech-to-help-security-industry-fend-off-hackers>

⁸ <https://www.wired.com/story/deepfake-porn-is-out-of-control/> and <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-europe-66877718> and <https://www.bbc.com/news/uk-politics-67518511> and <https://www.dw.com/en/can-india-tackle-deepfakes/a-67791106> and <https://www.mcafee.com/blogs/privacy-identity-protection/artificial-imposters-cybercriminals-turn-to-ai-voice-cloning-for-a-new-breed-of-scam/>

- There needs to be more education, literacy, and awareness of fraud and cybersecurity issues among the public and users. Such efforts done well can complement the technical aspects to detect the true information from the fake one.
- Importantly, there should be more investment in security and safety research with a long-term focus on principled research on the secure and safe design of AI methods.

Discussion highlights

Q: What kind of a policy recommendation could we have for more open datasets where researchers are more certain that they're not going to become at risk in using these?

A: It is unclear if alignment can be achieved with better curation. Many current theories suspect that, in the context of image generation models, even with a very good data set you would not necessarily generate certain types of images easily. On the matter of liability, if a researcher is using a dataset, they are probably responsible for the outcomes of the model. To obtain a higher level of transparency, accountability, and safety of the models, we would require a much higher investment to actually get clean, reliable, and safe data.

Automated misinformation and computational propaganda

It is now possible to generate junk news sites fast with a lot of text and hundreds of pages in less than a day or hour with AI, allowing anyone to populate thousands of domains at scale. In Argentina's elections this year, both contesting political parties used AI to generate text and images for disseminating their point of view. It is a worrying trend that can persist in other places.

The misinformation data most of the time begins to be tested in the dark or deep web. Then it's consolidated in junk news domains that exist to host and disseminate false information. When users find such websites through search engines, it is not surprising that they trust them as good information.

Transdisciplinary teams consisting of experts in information science, computational sociology, engineering, and data science are trying to understand the automation of computational propaganda. Studying the impact of misinformation in several fields, such as environment and climate change, political conspiracy, political-business partnerships, and recommendation algorithms shows their dangers and impacts on societies.

Researchers collect data from the communication and information ecosystems, including Twitter, Instagram, Facebook, YouTube, public groups on WhatsApp, Google Ads, Meta Ads, and media and junk news outlets. Understanding how misinformation is organised and how it is shared among all the systems and communications platforms offers a glimpse into the digital propaganda machinery (Ferrara, 2023; Pasquetto et al, 2022).

Automated accounts or bots are one of the most common methods for propagating misinformation on social media. Bots usually mimic human behaviour to spread a particular point of view, misleading the public with content recommendations. They play a disproportionate role in spreading misinformation, controlling social interactions, and influencing and manufacturing public opinion during elections and public discussions about important topics.

For example, when researchers mapped the network of tweets and Twitter accounts from 2019 regarding the Amazonian rainforest fires, they found a very polarised discourse. One side was the far-right government supporters, and the other side was from users and media with progressive agenda, both spreading a lot of misinformation. Researchers found that 60% of the tweets and information came from bots.

Moreover, it is already difficult to distinguish between bots and humans (Ferrara, 2023). With AI, the bot behaviour is evolving making them more sophisticated. Evolving AI algorithms increase challenges in the social media and information ecosystem. Sophisticated AI-generated content makes it impossible to distinguish between humans and bots. Bots also employ advanced tactics to evade detection. They can also change their behaviour. For example, bots in the early days posted a lot of content within a short amount of time, but now their behaviours have changed intelligently.

Some machine learning, deep learning, and botnet approaches help differentiating between a bot and human behaviours. The most famous tool, the Botometer⁹ developed by a German University, is widely used; however, it does not work very well for non-English language accounts. Researchers at the University of Rio de Janeiro developed the AI detection system Gotcha to understand the Brazilian digital ecosystems for bots (Santini, 2023). They used datasets consisting of 3000 Twitter accounts selected by terms and keywords related to recent events in Brazil between 2018 and 2023. The accounts went through manual annotations for strengthening training and testing modules. When they applied the Botometer to this dataset, the bot detection was poor. On the contrary, Gotcha built on manual annotation performed much better at distinguishing automated systems. They continue to rebuild Gotcha by adding more data and refining the behaviour as the detection tool to tackle ever-evolving bots.

Effective social bot detection needs to be scalable to handle large volumes of data and operate in real time. Social bot detection techniques must balance the need for accuracy while preserving user privacy and avoiding false positives that could harm innocent users. There is a growing challenge presented by the restricted access to platform Application Programming Interfaces (APIs), which increasingly limits the data available for research and detection mechanisms. The lack of transparency from social media platforms regarding their content curation, recommendation algorithms, and monetisation strategies poses significant obstacles to academic research in the development of effective detection systems.

While LLMs could be useful for combating misinformation through detection, they also add challenges through intentional generation (Chen & Shu, 2023), by creating rumours, fake news, clickbait, and

⁹ <https://www.rand.org/research/projects/truth-decay/fighting-disinformation/search/items/botometer.html>

propaganda, thus creating misinformation by mistake because the training data was either bad or generated by random text.

Key policy considerations

- It is important to verify the human users through authentication.
- The focus should be on tracing the content origin to control dubious sources.
- There should be resources available to develop tools to detect AI-generated content, especially for non-English content as current models struggle with them.
- Filtering advertisers and creating a safe list of compliant advertisers should be the norm with scrutinising political ads as the common monetisation tactics used by the industry.
- Long-term research support will increase trust and safety in AI.
- There should be policies to hold the platforms accountable for the contents, especially when the origin is not available, potentially making it false.
- Regulations must be implemented for data quality standards in AI language models based on international consensus by defining critical criteria and minimum prerequisites for dataset availability for utilisation. This should also include regulatory guidance for companies involved in the production, validation, and deployment of AI language for general use.

Discussion highlights

Q: How realistic is it to expect authentication of human users? Is it meaningful and technologically possible and organisationally feasible?

A: This is being discussed by many organisations. It might be a challenge. But it's one way to follow the data in a way that might be safe for the users if you are relating it to an actual human being. One option for that, instead of analysing who is human, is the platform who has this data showing what is a bot, what is automatic, how could the platforms provide this information.

AI and biochemical science, misuse, and 'reproducibility' crisis

Biological risks associated with the misuse of AI have been identified as a huge safety concern. AI capabilities in the biochemical sciences are far-reaching with large language models, biological design tools, and automation contributing to major advances (Carter et al, 2023). The potential magnitude of the impact and risks in governance and reproducibility concerns both heavily talked about large foundational models and smaller AI models.

LLMs

LLMs and chatbots help scientists and non-experts understand technical topics. Scientists at different career stages use them from understanding research topics to collaborating with interdisciplinary teams in

interpreting concepts from different fields. These tools also help design and troubleshoot scientific experiments and write computer codes.

While LLMs lower the barriers to science accessibility, they also contribute to the misinformation ecosystem. The models can be misused to suggest dubious scientific claims. On a more sinister side, LLMs can make recommendations on choosing, obtaining, manipulating, scaling, and delivering biological weapons. They can also be powerful tools for producing disinformation that could alter the course of natural pandemics or biosecurity threats (Ada Lovelace Institute, 2023).

Biological design tools

Several AI tools help scientists design biological parts and systems, such as synthetic chemicals and organisms (Callaway, 2022). Such capabilities escalate the risk of bioweapon design where the blueprint for generating highly toxic chemicals, proteins, and pathogens is available easily (Chattopadhyay et al, 2024; Lewis et al, 2019)

Automation

Automation in science benefits the community where streamlined repetitive laboratory tasks can be done by computers and sophisticated robotic systems. Other research tasks such as experimental designs and analysing results can also be automated in certain fields, helping scientists in scaling up their work. However, automation can improve the chances of misuse in the hands of the wrong players, such as testing and producing thousands of bioweapon designs at scale in a short amount of time.

Challenges in risk-benefit assessment

There are currently no tools or frameworks to test the biological safety of different AI tools. Biologists, AI developers, and biosecurity experts on their own are incapable of building and testing them. Therefore, developing these tools requires extensive cross-disciplinary expertise to solve complex questions in biosecurity. Because of the huge biosecurity benefits of such tools, overregulation could be less favourable than under regulation.

The harms associated with AI-Bio can be catastrophic; however, people often disagree on their plausibility because they are hard to test. Therefore, biosecurity experts are often reluctant to explicitly discuss them to avoid information hazards. This is particularly challenging because AI developers can't create safeguards around these unknown harms. Moreover, risks associated with one tool might increase manifold when used with other tools or capabilities. In that instance, risk assessment for a tool in isolation might not provide the severity of the risk.

Key policy considerations

- Evaluation of models by third parties is a popular recommendation. When the model is fully developed, it is better to assess its potential risks before releasing it for public use. However, the evaluation standards and who is fit to evaluate the models should be determined. This process can also be very expensive and there should be guidelines on who should pay. If the cost of compliance is high, it might discourage people from developing very useful AI.
- Self-evaluation by model developers is an alternative suggestion that would be cheaper and easier. However, there is a conflict of interest with this approach.
- Introducing liability for harm is another option that can prove to be a stronger incentive for developers to think more realistically about the risks and employ a conservative stance. Who should be liable in the AI development chain, particularly when a foundational model is fine-tuned and incorporated into a bad application by a different developer needs to be determined. In more harmful applications like AI-assisted bioweapon development, assigning liability will be impossible if the information about which tool was used and altered and who did it is unknown.
- Monitoring and regulating access to large amounts of compute and infrastructure could be another regulatory option. A predictable caveat with this strategy is that AI developers could turn towards more friendly regulatory environments and countries. This could also harm equitable access, particularly if this puts barriers to sharing compute resources with other lower middle-income countries with less purchasing power.
- There are suggestions about regulating or banning high-risk AI applications in biology. However, defining high-risk applications might be challenging. Further, many high-risk applications might be necessary for health, economic, and environmental benefits.
- Restricted access to certain types of data, such as the genomes of infectious diseases and toxins could prevent misuse. This approach could limit AI developments in places with restrictions and massive downsides in disease control and drug and vaccine developments at the global scale. Not sharing genome sequences of new viruses could diminish global disease detection and surveillance efforts in populations. Therefore, this strategy might turn out to be more harmful than useful.
- Screening orders of DNA for hazards might be a viable option because AI-designed toxins or viruses are harmless unless the relevant DNA sequence gets synthesised. Therefore, this could be a better intervention strategy than controlling AI access. However, screening DNA for hazards is a voluntary practice and there are no verification systems available at the moment. There is also a growing concern that AI can design sequences that can circumvent current screening tools.
- Having a vulnerability disclosure process that safeguards sensitive information from becoming public, similar to extant cybersecurity processes, could help with risk identification and mitigation. For example, when a risk is identified instead of going to the media and revealing it to everyone, there could be a better reporting framework about who should know about the risks first and how they should access information.

Discussion highlights

Q: Are there any examples of regulated information tools?

A: There is a long history of what should and shouldn't be published. For example, one can make a viable virus from DNA ordered from a company. There was a huge backlash around that because it is very easy to access and manufacture dangerous pathogens. However, such examples are reactive where the information becomes public and gets retracted only after an outcry.

Sustainability in AI (critiques on voluntary initiatives, potential policy options)

Green AI practices are a timely topic relevant for scientists in all research areas. The first step in sustainable AI use is to measure and quantify the environmental impact of an AI model by tracking carbon emissions (de Vries, 2023; Kaack et al, 2022; Pasek et al, 2023; Sasha Luccioni & Hernandez-Garcia, 2023; Schwartz et al, 2020; Strubell et al, 2019). These quantifications can then be compared with equivalent AI models in carbon emissions and energy consumption.

However, several technical hurdles make it difficult to compare different AI models (Cellard & Parker, 2024). AI systems are distributed with various specificities at both software and hardware levels. How they consume local energy varies too. Additionally, metrics standardisation for energy consumption also differs. For example, the International Electrotechnical Commission ISO, Green Software Foundation, and French AFNOR are all working towards standardising the measurement and reporting methods.

Cost-benefit analysis

In these efforts, there needs to be a cost-benefit analysis to evaluate the environmental cost of a given model if it offers economic, cultural, and social benefits (Godard, 2004; Luccioni et al, 2020). Similar to transport and health policymaking, such analysis can ensure the environmental costs are not disproportionate to the benefits of a given AI application. However, there are many obstacles to cost-benefit analysis for sustainable AI. First, there is no academic or policy literature on applying cost-benefit analysis to AI and its environmental impact. There are also no robust and standardised metrics and methods available yet to quantify the costs. Therefore, determining what are the benefits and how to evaluate them for any cost-benefit analysis remains challenging. Nonetheless, when such methods become available, there needs to be a regulation process that achieves consensus around metrics, methods, and environmental impact to avoid giving undue advantage to any special interest groups.

There is a broad consensus throughout the social sciences around the problems associated with cost-benefit analysis. It exemplifies an economic style of reasoning that tends to focus on monetisation, stifles ambitious environmental changes, and limits rights and equality measures (Berman, 2022). To circumvent some of these pitfalls, cost-benefit analysis needs to be contextualised in local views for very specific applications of AI. The more clear the applications, the more solid cost-benefit analysis can be achieved.

Moreover, methods and instruments carrying out such analysis remain fragile because the environmental benefits of AI tend to be overestimated while their environmental impact assessments are underestimated

(Ligozat et al, 2022). This happens because it is difficult to calculate AI's full ecological implications beyond carbon accounting. In particular, water consumption and biodiversity issues around data centres are neglected aspects of environmental costs in AI. Further, it is imperative to stop treating non-humans like water, energy, and biodiversity as resources (Taffel et al, 2022). They should be viewed as conditions required for living and flourishing.

Key policy considerations

- There is already a set of best practices coming from the AI literature that could be used to support AI developers in reducing company emissions. This bottom-up approach will force best practices on people responsible for AI development. For example, anyone developing an AI model should choose data centres with the greenest energy grids and sustainable GPUs and cloud providers.
- Harnessing the power of open science and open-source practices, developers can reuse pre-trained models and other available resources to reduce computing costs. For example, Hugging Face is one of the big advocates of this approach to reduce carbon emissions.
- Researchers should disclose emissions associated with AI and machine learning results in conferences, grants, and publications.
- AI developers can also schedule AI computing tasks within data centres in a way that does not saturate the local electricity demand.
- It is crucial to study cost-benefit analysis in other domains and try to identify pitfalls when applied to AI to develop best practices. Best practices and cost-benefit instruments can be very effective if strong quantification, standardisation, and accountability exist. However, these practices must be co-designed with AI scientists.

Discussion highlights

Q: The cost-benefit analysis has been heavily criticised because monetisation is a core feature. It reduces a complex multi-objective problem to a single objective which is money. Many things are difficult to evaluate in the environmental domain, especially to put a price tag.

A: A different strategy similar to large infrastructure deployment like making a new dam could be employed instead of the cost-benefit analysis. The way implications of the new dam on ecosystems, agriculture, hydropower, and water provision are considered should be applied to AI systems as well. Diverse stakeholders should also be involved in the decision-making process.

Promoting/communicating AI use in scientific communities

AI use in sciences creates new challenges in science publishing and communication (Merchant et al, 2023; Szymanski et al, 2023). Using AI in scientific literature contributes to the reproducibility crisis (Ball 2024), where many publications report data leakage problems with specific data creating incorrect results that get published in hundreds of papers (Kapoor & Narayanan, 2023).

There is another set of publications because of AI where AI big companies publish in other research areas. For example, Google AI researchers recently published work in chemistry identifying new materials using machine learning. This trend opens a general question. What should researchers teach to their students in the near future? Is there any room for teaching theories or the focus should be on statistical and programming approaches?

Peer review

Peer review is the pillar of internal evaluation in the scientific community (Kelly et al, 2014). In 2016 alone, almost 14 million reviews were undertaken to support the publication of close to 3 million articles (Johnson et al, 2018). A contested idea in peer review is whether AI has a role in this process. AI can aid peer review in several ways, such as analysing data, plagiarism check, data extraction, concept summarisation, editing, and proofreading. However, it is desirable to not replace humans in the entire process, and quality assessment should be done by humans. If such automatic peer review is done without humans, it must be transparent and declared.

Validating a scientific study costs a lot of energy and time. The selection of good reviewers and the time invested by reviewers guarantees good quality peer review. Typically, highly reputed journals have high rejection rates and high costs. On the contrary, low-reputation journals receive fewer submissions with much higher acceptance rates at low cost. AI-based peer review could help lower the publication cost but can compromise the quality of articles.

Peer review is done by humans simply because it creates a community of scientific experts who share common values, goals, scientific understanding, and ethical principles. When it comes to allowing AI in peer review, AI should be treated as a tool and should not replace human expertise.

Predatory publishing

There are predatory journals that do not produce realistic science and peer review. The number of predatory journals is growing faster than the number of traditional reliable journals (IAP, 2022; Liverpool, 2023). Some journals that are not predatory but still publish very low-quality peer-reviewed work (Hanson et al, 2023).

There is also a growth in papers authored by software algorithms marketed by private companies. It is difficult for publishers to recognize these papers. Many editors are afraid that this new phenomenon will reinforce unethical malpractice in producing scientific papers without any content.

Key policy considerations

- The time has come to create agencies for the evaluation of scientific publishers and publications, similar to rating agencies that produce records of the actions of banks, financial institutions, and companies. There needs to be a list of credible, serious, and transparent publishers.

- When publishers use AI, it must be declared and clearly stated whether AI produced the papers and revised data. AI will certainly be used in science communication, but that process must be fully transparent.
- The general problem with science these days is the overproduction of scientific papers. Not all of them are needed. The evaluation systems largely focus on quantity rather than quality. One solution could be people-based evaluations where a selection of studies from the same author are checked for quality and impact. Such a scenario could motivate researchers to publish fewer high-quality papers. The current scientific publishing system that incentivizes a publish-or-perish model needs to change.
- There is a huge amount of work coming out of all research sectors that use AI and ML approaches. On the other hand, many papers are also flagged for using AI to generate and manipulate data and analysis. It is often difficult to discriminate between AI-generated and AI-assisted content and publishers need to develop software and tools to identify such content.

Discussion highlights

Q: AI facilitates text generation easily. Why cannot researchers focus on generating scientific results and use AI to produce papers and science communication content?

A: In science, details are important. To explain a new theory, method, and scientific discovery in greater detail is impossible with AI because of the way it is designed.

Q: Should the EU change its open science policies?

A: There is a battle between open science and dark science. All public institutes are pushing for open science policies. On the other hand, Big Tech is working on not just AI but also biomedicine, material science, and other research areas. These companies function in complete darkness with a focus on controlling the future of science in all areas. There should be more focus on how to make the work coming out of these companies open and transparent. Paradoxically, knowledge generated by publicly funded researchers is made freely available to these companies, but nothing comes back to the public.

Diversity and inclusiveness in research

With the broader use of AI in society, how this technology affects disabilities and diverse demographics should be part of the AI policy. Currently, there are over 1.6 billion people with disabilities. Disabilities fall under a wide spectrum of physical, cognitive, and mental impairments underlying conditions specific to gender, age, and socioeconomic boundaries.

The support for people with disabilities is scant where approximately 80% of people either have no jobs or are not employed full-time (Brouwers, 2020; Chen et al, 2015; Touzet, 2023). Only 10% of people with mental

and cognitive conditions, such as autism spectrum disorders and Down syndrome have access to assistive technologies, including the novel ones driven by AI.

Ethically implemented algorithms and AI systems can help to eliminate some of these social barriers, making the lives of people with disabilities better (Garg & Sharma, 2020; Panjwani-Charania & Zhai, 2023). Over 120 technologies driven by AI support disabilities, including smart wheelchairs, walking sticks, bionic limbs, and other accommodation learning technologies. Smart dashboards for parents, robotics, and emotional recognition systems help people with cognitive disabilities (Kouroupa et al, 2022; Pennisi et al, 2016; Rakhymbayeva et al, 2021).

All of these solutions empower not only people with disabilities but contribute to positive economic and social impact for a broader society. For example, a technology for cognitive impairments can be used in mental health and educational ecosystems. They also create completely new experiences for other people, such as interactive creative environments that are developed for people living with autism, dyslexia, and attention deficit disorders. These technological spaces are available not just in the EU but also in the Middle East, specifically, Saudi Arabia, Qatar, and the United Arab Emirates.

Even though AI could support disability, there are many issues.¹⁰ Because every disability is unique, the physical, visual, hearing, cognitive, and communication experiences differ. Often available algorithms and systems bring developments that do not align with conditions (Goggin & Soldatić, 2022). For example, people with facial differences or asymmetry, different gestures, and feature impairment are not properly identified by AI systems and robots (Touzet, 2023).

These issues are pervasive in hiring platform screenings where employability scores are affected for people with disabilities due to the limited time frames, lack of accessibility, and difficulties with input recognition (Newman-Griffis et al, 2022; Tilmes, 2022). Moreover, language-based systems like generative AI that rely on public datasets build negative connotations and sentiments around keywords and phrases related to disability (Hassan et al, 2021; Narayanan Venkit et al, 2023). For example, some governmental agencies were alleged to use personal social media data without consent to confirm disability statuses for pensions and social protection payments in the United States (Packin, 2021).

AI systems can also affect accessibility to public services when they are unable to recognise impairments of limbs, speech patterns, and craniofacial patterns in uploaded documents. There are also concerns in the social network settings recognizing disabled people's actions as suspicious or automated. Lastly, AI technologies can impinge on the rights of persons with disabilities where the police and autonomous security systems may falsely recognize assistive devices as dangerous objects.

It is important to note that algorithms do not create biases themselves, but rather rely on existing issues in society (Gallegos et al, 2023; Pagano et al, 2023; Wambsganss et al, 2023; Yang et al, 2023). Therefore, the

¹⁰ <https://www.ohchr.org/en/documents/thematic-reports/ahrc4952-artificial-intelligence-and-rights-persons-disabilities-report>

frameworks and policy guidelines should focus on inherent societal bias (Ouellette, 2019) and find ways to work with these technologies with the goal of including people with disabilities.

Key policy considerations

- There is a lack of data and access since individuals with disabilities were excluded from statistics affecting modern datasets. There is a model generalisation where most technologies address the broader population as a uniform population with ideal health conditions. Unfortunately, this brings the wrong outcomes for specific conditions. Therefore, the system design must include sufficient data, experiments, and evidence on the missing demographic.
- Until today, there was no single mention of people with disabilities in the EU AI Act or any other policies focused on the technology. Cooperating with the European Disability Forum and other organisations helps build guidelines to include excluded groups.
- Disability is not a monolith. It is intersectional with a variety of cognitive, sensory, and physical impairments that affect specific groups. For example, there are unique conditions for girls and some disabilities are more prevalent in certain socioeconomic groups. Each technology is a multi-stakeholder endeavour requiring the adoption of guidelines through a process that must involve many people and not just technology developers.
- The EU AI Act and similar documents need to specify the risk categories not only for the broader population but also for specific cases and groups for manipulative scenarios. The invisible risks and addictive design need to be specified.
- There needs to be a careful discussion about how governmental and non-governmental agencies operate with the data coming from groups with disabilities and consider ethics and privacy checks.

Discussion highlights

Q: What are the key challenges and solutions specific to the use of AI in scientific research for better inclusion of people with disabilities and health conditions?

A: The majority of the medical applications do not represent people with disabilities. They are not part of any data, therefore, any type of predictive AI tool does not work for them. If they are included in the dataset, it is only physical disabilities in most cases. Similarly, in health conditions, there is gender bias where medical tests are focused on men. Since women are not part of such data and physical manifestations of autism and other cognitive disabilities differ between girls and boys, the AI self-learning systems are not inclusive and efficient.

To address deficiencies in AI research for disabilities, the first goal should be representation. For example, many companies and scientific groups developing platforms that target cognitive disabilities proudly recruit up to 75% of their team who live with a particular condition. These team members specifically help build the common vocabulary and provide a basic understanding of the conditions. This approach should be replicated at governance and policy-making stages to integrate people with disabilities in the decision-making.

Summary of discussions

Among the policy recommendations concerning the timely uptake of AI in scientific work, experts had a few major considerations and disagreements that must be entertained in the EU AI Act drafting.

Is the CERN-ish model for AI viable?

To attract talent back from the industry and provide much more attractive research conditions, many researchers favour the idea of building a CERN-like institute for AI. Most of the scientific community converges around this idea, which represents a big research infrastructure providing access to resources, compute, and data along with all kinds of services for scientists to do better science using AI.

This project will be similar to an Oppenheimer project where the institute is created with an urgency highlighting specific goals and massive funding resources. Tech companies have achieved this in a short amount of time. If the European Union cannot do this, there will be serious constraints for AI research. A possible concern with building a new institution is what if questions and AI ecosystems change by the time the institute is ready.

However, many researchers disagree on whether a CERN-ish institution will help bring the talent back. Experts also caution against removing EU researchers from their home countries. They consider keeping them in the countries while creating a network as a better solution. Others believe that large, dedicated AI compute centres should be placed where researchers are instead of building a big institution. Such a strong distributed network within Europe can be a strong asset without the need for moving all the top researchers.

From a geopolitical perspective, this is a good idea because Sam Altman from OpenAI and Jensen Huang from NVIDIA employ divide and rule policy to maintain monopoly in AI. The European market power to buy expensive GPUs and AI services is limited because big companies and non-EU countries currently hoard them. Under the CERN-ish policy recommendation, the European Commission can establish a consolidated listing of science and engineering that require GPUs. Then, similar to the COVID-19 vaccine negotiations, the EU institute can maximise the bargaining power by working with the manufacturers.

Some experts disagree that the CERN model is a good idea. CERN is constructed around a specific infrastructure that nobody else can have in its own country. For AI, the Internet and computers are available everywhere. The knowledge and innovation communities and their flagship projects across the EU with funding for academics, industries, and private institutions could be a better system.

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Workshop participants

Expert participants

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- **Anna Fabijańska**, Lodz University of Technology, Poland
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- **Hubert Brychczyński**, science writer
- **Alaa Jbour**, Communications Manager
- **Rudolf Hielscher**, SAPEA Coordinator

Science writer

Sejal Davla, consultant and science writer, Canada

Workshop methods

Expert selection

In the context of the request for Advice on the topic 'Successful and timely uptake of Artificial Intelligence in science in the EU' SAPEA issued a call for nominations on 18 July 2023, describing the scope, timeline and expertise required. The call for nominations was sent via the academy networks to their member academies, who were invited to nominate experts following the procedure described in the SAPEA Quality Assurance Guidelines¹¹. Experts involved in the workshop were selected from the list of nominees. Additional experts were also identified through desk research by the academy networks. The list of areas of expertise that should be covered in the workshop was established in coordination with the SAM Secretariat and the member of the SAPEA working group in charge of key area 4.

The experts were selected by SAPEA and the member of the working group in charge of key area 4 on the basis of scientific excellence and disciplinary requirements as a priority, taking into account commitment and time availability, and the criteria set out in our strategy of diversity and inclusiveness:

- inter- and multidisciplinary
- involvement in the wider scientific community;
- inclusion of early- and mid-career researchers
- gender balance
- wide geographical coverage, including from Widening countries

The final group of experts who attended the workshop included 38% of female experts. 31% of attending experts were early-career and 50% mid-career researchers. 19% of experts came from Widening Countries. The following countries were represented by the experts: Belgium, Brazil, Czechia, France, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, United Kingdom, Switzerland.

Workshop process

Experts received the scoping paper along with the questions posed in key area 4 in advance of the workshop. They were asked to present on the scientific topic of interest, related to their area of expertise. In line with the SAPEA principle of transparency, workshop expert participants were asked to declare any conflict of interest and any interest that might be perceived by SAPEA as a conflict of interest in relation to this scientific topic at the beginning of their presentations.

¹¹ SAPEA, Science Advice for Policy by European Academies. (2023). Quality assurance guidelines and procedures on science advice for policy and society. Berlin: SAPEA. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8329539>

Experts also received specific instructions about the format of presentations:

- listing the scientific publications cited in the presentations
- preparing the content of the presentation by drawing on their own research but also on their broad knowledge of the field
- keeping the confidentiality of participants until the publication of the report

The report summarising the workshop was prepared by SAPEA and sent to all experts present for feedback before publication. To encourage openness and the sharing of information, the public summary report was prepared in an anonymous, non-attributed style.

Workshop programme

- *09:05 Background to the request*
- *09:10 Introductory remarks*
- 09:15 Actors of the 'scientific and research communities across the EU' - research undertaken in 'private' labs
- 09:35 What is 'responsible and timely' AI uptake in science in the EU?
- 09:55 Geopolitics of AI: what implications for responsible science?
- 10:15 How do AI and the Open Source approach to AI in science affect the cybersecurity and security spaces?
- *10:35 General discussion*
- *10:50 Break*
- 11:05 Automated misinformation – computational propaganda
- 11:25 AI and biochemical science, misuse, and reproducibility
- 11:45 Sustainability in AI (critiques on voluntary initiatives, potential policy options)
- 12:05 Promoting/communicating AI use in scientific communities
- 12:25 Diversity and inclusiveness in research
- *12:45 General discussion*
- *13:05 Wrap up and conclusions*
- *13:10 Next steps and closing*

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